

**Leadership Styles influencing the morale of
the Millennial/Generation Z employees: A
study on the worker of the future in
Singapore.**

by

Dr. Teng Kok Leong / Singapore

Roehampton Business School

15.05.2023

Abstract

This dissertation is on the academic research on leadership and motivation. A thorough literature overview on both the Millennial and Generation Z generation is found in Chapter 2, along with information on societal perceptions, attitudes and behaviours, and managerial issues related to these generation. The motivations for the Millennial and Generation Z generation's attitudes and behaviours, management issues, and how to effectively lead both the Millennial and Generation Z generation are briefly covered in this chapter. An examination of the literature on the type of leadership, transformational leadership, actualized leadership profiling and agile leadership is included in Chapter 2's explanation of the theoretical framework.

Since the value of an organization's people resources is its greatest competitive advantage, investing in their motivation is essential to achieving superior operational performance. The motivation of employees and the rewards that go along with it have become a common problem for organizations and management alike since the advent of scientific management about 100 years ago (Hansen, et al., 2002). It is predicted that Millennial and Generation Z will make up more than half of the world's workforce by 2020. Considering this, this study investigates how motivation and related rewards affect Millennial and Generation Z employees in the workplace.

For both generation age cohorts, 214 individuals were polled. The information gathered was based on the thoughts of the respondents about the ideas of leadership, incentive, and rewards. It was discovered that respondents in the Millennial and Generation Z generations preferred non-monetary compensation to other monetary compensation, yet they were intrinsically motivated by their work. Several recommendations are based on the findings and consider the implications of this study for both scholars and practitioners. A motivated employee will perform better and align their own aspirations with the organization's goals; hence it is important for organizations to understand what drives their youngest employees.

Declaration

The work I have submitted is my own effort. I certify that any and all the material in this Dissertation, that is *not* my own work, has been identified and acknowledged.

No materials are included for which a degree has been previously conferred upon me.

Signed: *Teng Koh Leong*

Date: 15 MAY 2023

Contents

1. Introduction	6
1.1. Overview	6
1.2. Research problem	8
1.3. Research motivation	9
1.4. Research questions	9
1.5. Research objectives	10
1.6. Significance of the research	11
2. Literature review	12
2.1 Leadership, communication, and social influence: a theory of resonance, activation, and cultivation	12
2.2 Actualized Leadership	15
2.3 Agile Business Leadership Methods For Industry 4.0	19
2.4 Millennial Generation and Generation Z	24
2.5 Research Hypotheses	28
3. Research Design and Methodology	29
3.1 Research Approach	29
3.2 Research Methods	32
3.3 Questionnaire Formulation	33
3.4 Questionnaire Design	34
3.5 Target Audience and Data Collection	39
3.6 Survey Pilot Testing	39
3.7 Data Analysis Plan	40
3.8 Ethical Issue	42
4. Results, analysis and evaluation of findings	43
4.1 Demographic Profile	43
4.2 Mean And Standard Deviation	45
4.3 Reliability Test	50
4.4 Hypothesis Testing	51
4.4.1 Hypothesis 1	53
4.4.2 Hypothesis 2	57
4.4.3 Hypothesis 3	62
4.4.4 Hypothesis 4	66

4.4.5	Hypothesis Analysis Summary	70
5.	Conclusions And Recommendations	71
5.1	Research Question and Objective One	71
5.2	Research Question and Objective Two	73
5.3	Research Question and Objective Three	75
5.4	Recommendations For Future study	76
5.5	Research Limitations	77
	BIBLIOGRAPHY	78
	Appendices	86
A -	List of Tables	86
B -	List of Figures	88
C -	Final Survey	89
D -	Research Data	98

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. OVERVIEW

Many businesses nowadays struggle to find and keep staff while competing successfully in the highly competitive globalized market. It is thought that globalization and its incredibly demanding transnational characteristics are the primary causes of this problem. However, one efficient approach of making organization successful is developing effective interaction between the leader and its followers, who are in this case, employees. These are the elements in enhancing success and productivity inside the organization. Leaders make use of numerous occasions to advance a company's objective and vision, successfully convey them to their followers, and develop an implementation plan (Chhotray, Sivertsson & Tell, 2018). Effective leaders should strive to inspire and uplift their team members, as well as support and encourage their mental health at work.

Today's leaders must be able to relate to each generation of employees and comprehend their needs. They will veer closer to irrelevance if they don't. The nature of the workforce will keep evolving. The older generations need to have a better awareness of the Generation Z's entire educational, economic, social, and political makeup, according to experts (Benítez, Sánchez, Bermúdez & Rydman, 2022). Understanding which leadership philosophies encourage employee motivation in members of both the Millennial and the Generation Z is crucial considering this. The manager-employee relationship may be impacted by this study. Addressing the difficulties managers face in inspiring and developing employees from the Millennial and Generation Z may be helpful (Benítez, Sánchez, Bermúdez & Rydman, 2022). By addressing this issue, the workplace culture might improve. As a result, there would be a higher rate of employee retention and corporate social responsibility participation, leading to a more productive atmosphere. A company's profits may rise because of improved productivity.

Addressing these issues can also spur beneficial social change in the neighbourhoods where the employees live and work. The growth of one leader may have a substantial effect on others, which may then influence the larger workforce and community, so amplifying the positive social change. Another crucial finding of this study was the identification of leadership philosophies that work well with the both the Millennial and Generation Z. Given that Millennial and Generation Z are now Singapore's largest generation, surpassing the baby boomer generation, this understanding is necessary for organizations to be sustainable (Petro, et al., 2021).

The rapport between a boss and employee has a direct bearing on the employee's drive and commitment (Harlez, 2015). A noncollaborative manager who adopts a dictatorial or micromanaging style of management won't foster a positive work atmosphere (Lee, 2021). According to Lee (2021), this will undermine staff morale and diminish motivation. A manager must prioritize energizing staff members and act as a mentor and team leader who motivates team members to be productive (Lee, 2021). According to Amabile & Kramer (2011), managers have a direct impact on their employees' motivation. The capacity to communicate with, inspire, and lead the workforce is more crucial than functional skill when in a management post, even when a person's technical experience may be the reason that person gained a management position (Amabile & Kramer, 2011).

The best way to define motivation is as a potent instrument for driving individuals toward achieving a specific goal. The ability of motivation to help people achieve their essential human needs, such as self-esteem, a sense of belonging, acknowledgment, and other basic wants, is another goal of motivation (Amabile & Kramer, 2011). This report will briefly describe the most well-known theories of motivation that can demonstrate its significance. First, according to McGregor's theory of X and Y, there are two distinct categories of people: those motivated by remuneration and rewards (X group) and those who desire greater responsibility and creativity in their work (Y group) (Schermerhorn, 2011). The second assertion made by Herzberg's theory is that organizations can use both motivators and hygienic elements to affect motivation at work (Schermerhorn, 2011). Motivators are internal elements, including responsibility and tough job, that motivate employees to work more.

In connection to that, successful organizations need leaders for a variety of reasons. Every firm should have a powerful leader who can positively influence the actions of every employee. When done well, it significantly affects how eagerly employees are to help the organization achieve its goals, mission, and vision (Harlez, 2015). Innovative ideas are communicated by leaders, who also play a key role in putting them into action through their workforce (Lee, 2021).

1.2. RESEARCH PROBLEM

We are all currently faced with the wonderful opportunities and challenges of coexisting with five generations in the workforce. According to the Awang (2022), below is the 5 Generations and their age as of 2022: -

- Generation Z (Born between 1997 to 2013) (age 10 to 25 years old)
- Millennials (Born between 1981 to 1996) (age 26 to 41 years old)
- Generation X (Born between 1965 to 1980) (age 42 to 57 years old)
- Baby Boomers (Born between 1946 to 1964) (age 58 to 76 years old)
- Traditionalists (Born before 1945)

Wherever there is intergenerational animosity, the young and the old commonly exchange insults like "boomers are out of touch," "Millennial are entitled," and "Gen Zs are softies" (Awang, et al., 2022). These broad remarks, according to the experts whose opinions were sought, not only split generations but also create divisions where there are frequently none since they lump millions of unique people together and ascribe labels to them (Awang, et al., 2022).

According to the Singapore Statistics data, there are 17.1% of the Singapore residents are in the Generation Z age group and 23.4% of the Singapore residents are in the Millennial Age group. These add up to be more than the Generation X age group who would be the leaders of the company. The Millennial generation is difficult for managers to relate to and manage, and they frequently fail to effectively motivate these employees (Segal, et al., 2022). As a result, those firms can find it challenging to hire or keep individuals from the Millennial age. The Generation Z are growing up to be the next generation employees. There are growing interest to find out this generation motivation towards work. Moreover, there was little research on the leadership philosophies that work best with Millennial and Generation Z employees (Segal, et al., 2022). Which leadership styles encourage motivation in the Millennial and Generation Z is the specific issue that is to be studied.

1.3. RESEARCH MOTIVATION

Research on the styles of leadership that Generation Z workers react to most favourably is lacking. (Sauser and Sims, 2013). With this study, I aimed to determine the best practices for managing Millennial and Generation Z employees while acknowledging the difficulties that leaders currently face (Benítez, Sánchez, Bermúdez & Rydman, 2022). This was accomplished by investigating the leadership philosophies that inspire Millennial and Generation Z employees. Gaining expertise in this area of leadership will give leaders the tools they need to adjust to the distinctive characteristics of Millennial and Generation Z employees. This may therefore place firms in a position to improve their cultural fit and boost output and performance (Sauser and Sims, 2013). In addition, with my current role as Associate Director of the company, this research does motivate me to find out what the new Generation employees need, and this would help me create a better working environment for the employees.

1.4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

According to Sirisilla (2022), to uncover answers is the aim of research. Not the general issues we want to address, but the more specific issues that define the studies. As a result, having the proper conversations about the correct subjects becomes essential. For a research project to get off to a good start, a strong research question is required (Bouchrika, et al., 2022). It provides the study investigation with direction and a clear goal to focus on. If we comprehend the components of a strong research inquiry, we will generate fresh thoughts and pick up new research methods (Sirisilla, et al., 2022).

A strong research question makes the issue clear and supports the hunt for an answer. The study's design is guided by an effective research topic (Sirisilla, et al., 2022). It also assists in determining the research's nature and specific objectives. Research questions pinpoint the issue we are attempting to address and focus on the study's findings so that others can understand (Bouchrika, et al., 2022). Therefore, it is useful to break the research into manageable pieces to achieve the objectives and answer the opening question. Below are the specific questions generated for this research.

RQ1. Is Transformational or Team leadership style preferred by the Millennial and Generation Z employees?

RQ2. Is Agile or Actualized leadership style preferred by the Millennial and Generation Z employees?

RQ3. What are the motivation factors for Millennial and Generation Z employees?

1.5. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This quantitative study's objective was to investigate the leadership philosophies that help Millennial and Generation Z employees feel motivated at work. Leadership styles that could be transformational, team, actualised, and agile-like were the independent variables. Employee motivation was the dependent variable.

Employees from the Millennial and Generation Z who worked in offices made up the study's population in Singapore. The study's findings may lead to beneficial modifications in how personnel are managed and led. This might benefit society in a variety of ways throughout an organization. Through the social connections that engage the impacted employees, this could potentially have an indirect good societal change outside of the firm.

RO1. To identify the leadership style to manage Millennial and Generation Z employee.

The first research objective is to identify the leadership style (transformational or team) to manage the Millennial and Generation Z. Leaders could adapt the changes and able to manage the new generation employees efficiently.

RO2. To identify the modern leadership style to manage Millennial and Generation Z employee.

The second research objective is to identify the modern leadership style (Actualized or Agile) that can manage Millennial and Generation Z. Leaders could review this information, analyse their leading style and possible change to manage the new generation employees effectively.

RO3. To discover the motivation factor for Millennial and Generation Z employees

The third research objective is to find out the motivation factors for the Millennial and Generation Z employees. With the factors, it would help leaders and the HR Manager to cater for the specific needs and possible using these to increase the retention rate of the company.

1.6. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH

The key factors influencing an employee's motivation are their workplace and the company culture (Harlez, 2015). Employee motivation tends to be constrained in organizational cultures that adhere to a traditional management paradigm that inhibits employee empowerment (Harlez, 2015). For instance, companies that favour an autocratic leadership style promote behaviour that is repressive and dictatorial (Chhotray, Sivertsson & Tell, 2018). These leadership philosophies may have a detrimental effect on employees' output, motivation, and morale, which may result in employees quitting the company (Chhotray, Sivertsson & Tell, 2018).

The results of the quantitative study may contribute to our knowledge of leadership, particularly as it relates to leading and managing Millennial and Generation Z. When it comes to the manager/employee interaction, these findings may lead to positive social change for academics as they add to a field with limited body of research and for practitioners. The study was a novel addition that may lead to practical applications for leading and managing Millennial and Generation Z employees to increase employee engagement in a company.

With a focus on Millennial and Generation Z, those people born between 1985 and 1996 and between 1997 and 2012 respectively, the study will investigate their expectations that will help in producing positive organizational outcomes. It is crucial for HR managers and business leaders to get ready for the future workforce and align their behaviour with Generation Z characteristics as they are the youngest workforce. Understanding the new behaviours and ways of thinking of young people just entering the workforce can aid in the selection and hiring processes as well as their retention, which will help the business achieve sustainable growth (Awang, et al., 2022).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this chapter, summary of the leadership philosophies will be discussed. Different types of leadership styles from the literature will also be examined. The views and actions of the Millennial and Generation Z will be discussed in literature. There is, however, limited research on the most effective leadership philosophies for Millennial and Generation Z employees. In the literature study, we were also examining the factors that motivate Millennial and Generation Z employees' attitudes and behaviours as well as the management issues that these traits raise.

2.1 LEADERSHIP, COMMUNICATION, AND SOCIAL INFLUENCE: A THEORY OF RESONANCE, ACTIVATION, AND CULTIVATION

The first literature was written by Ruben and Gigliotti in 2019. Readers are urged by Ruben and Gigliotti to make decisions as prospective leaders and followers with a more sophisticated understanding of social impact and communication. The authors examine perplexing issues such as how some leaders in the work environment, neighbourhood, or national political scene manage to gather a sizable following of devoted supporters while appearing to lack the traits and abilities that most leadership specialists identify.

One of the enduring delusions about leadership is the assumption that certain people are more naturally born leaders than others. (Ruben and Gigliotti, 2019). The authors agreed the common assumption, that goes along with this point of view, is that a person's ability for leadership is mostly decided by their personality and has nothing to do with the experiences they have during their career. Another widely held belief is that being talkative and extroverted is necessary for influence. According to the authors, these actions are frequently linked to a tendency for being domineering which breeds opposition to the intended results and, over time, erodes any respect and influence a leader may otherwise have. In a variety of social influence circumstances, being skilful at selective communicative engagement and cautious judgment about with whom and when to emphasize one's opinions can be a very significant and effective talent.

The authors questioned why some social influence tactics seem to connect with some audiences instantaneously and rather organically, whereas chances to influence other constituencies might only present themselves over a longer period or not at all. The authors examine how viewpoints, words, and behaviours of a sender/leader and receiver/follower may resonate as well as how this resonance affects others' responses and reactions by examining the confluence of leadership and communication. The authors explained that it is possible to organize and synthesize these existing leadership theories in a variety of ways, including a scheme that they have found useful, and which

specifically focuses on classical theories, contemporary theories, competency theories, and communication theories. Also, with the concept of social influence at its core, this synthesis of popular leadership theories has revolutionized the way they view leadership.

The authors also raise the question of whether certain leadership techniques will always produce favourable results in a variety of contexts, circumstances, and cultures. The authors agreed that there are some knowledge and skill set that are important to leadership success in particular situations and contexts, but that there are also a number of general competencies that are typically important across situations, sectors, and cultures (Gigliotti, 2019; Goleman, 1998; Ruben, 2006). With the question on effective leadership, the authors believed that regardless of whether the results of their efforts are viewed as unpleasant or unwanted, either on purpose or by accident, people can still practice the kind of leadership that is effective, successful, or impactful by others.

According to the authors, the primary focus of the classic literature on leadership is on the characteristics, abilities, and/or guiding principles of the leader(s) in a variety of contexts. On this aspect, the authors have given the ideas of how earlier literature are researched on. The authors agreed that the essence of leadership, particularly transformational, and servant leadership, is being explored by more modern theories, while competency theories place emphasis on learning and strategically using knowledge and skills to identify and meet the needs of different contexts and situations for leadership.

Trait Approach	Skills Approach	Style approach	Situational Approach	Contingency Theory	Path-Goal Theory	Leader-Member Exchange Theory
Effective if have the below traits	Cultivated and developed	Attributes of individual	Circumstances at hand	Extending from Situational Approach	Accomplish desired Goals	Interaction between leaders and followers
Intelligence	Technical skill	Common set of behaviours	Demonstrate awareness	Matching between leader's style and context	Motivated through achievable goals	exchange related to positive outcome
Self-confidence / Integrity	Human skill	Importance of subordinates or followers	Different situation, different approach	Leader-member relations	Focus on Motivation	In-group Member vs out- group member
Determination	Conceptual skill	Attributes of individual			Focus on Motivation	Trust of leader

Table 1 : Leader's Approached and Theories (Ruben and Gigliotti, 2019).

According to the authors, an overview of the theories was described as shown in Table 1 above. In one of the classical leadership theories, some people were believed to have natural leadership traits that are crucial to leadership and set them apart from non-leaders (Ruben and Gigliotti, 2019). In the past, this trait approach has proven appealing due of its simplicity. According to the authors, however, this approach has received a lot of criticism since it makes the presumption that only people with certain fixed attributes can be successful leaders. The Skills approach of leadership focuses on the technical, interpersonal, and conceptual qualities necessary for efficient leadership.

The authors agreed that this skills approach fails to explain how certain skill patterns or skill variations have a discernible and predictable effect on overall leadership performance or effectiveness. An emphasis on a consistent set of behaviours, in a range of circumstances, is a key component of a style approach to leadership. Additionally, this method emphasizes how crucial followers and subordinates are in determining a leader's competence and the requirements of those people.

The authors contended that the relevance of specific leadership qualities depends on the situation at hand. This situational approach emphasizes the requirement for leaders to be able to show that they are cognizant of the context in which they are operating (Ruben and Gigliotti, 2019). This strategy implies that several leadership styles are required in various contexts. The author agreed that as extension to situational approach, contingency approach based on the leaders and its member relation. The authors further described the Path-Goal theory and the Leader-Member exchange theory which both emphasizes on motivation with the latter having the goal setting to motivate employee once it is achieved.

According to the authors, the ability of leaders to make a major difference in the lives of those they lead is the emphasis of transformational leadership. Transformational leaders exhibit a powerful influence that inspires followers to go above and beyond what is typically expected of them (Lee, 2021). The authors described that 'Idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration' are four essential components of transformative leadership. According to the servant leadership philosophy, servant leaders are individuals who put the interests of their followers above their own (Ruben and Gigliotti, 2019). Servant leadership gives a novel, perhaps counterintuitive, and unique approach to the use of power and influence because it makes benevolence the focal point of the leadership process.

According to the authors, team leadership approach investigates how dependent members of groups coordinate efforts and reach shared objectives. A team's leader is essential in identifying group weaknesses, implementing corrective measures, predicting environmental changes, and averting harmful ones (Lee, 2021). The authors agreed that this approach could however be the best leadership approach as many organizations are going into team management approach. As with other leadership approach, one significant critique of this approach is that it presents an incomplete list of the competencies required for effective team leadership, limited, and falls short of properly addressing the unique issues related to team dynamics (Ruben and Gigliotti, 2019).

In consideration, the authors suggested, in addition to theories, recognizing the significance of developmental effects in the learning of leadership qualities, approaches to leadership have developed from those that concentrated on a potential leader's nature abilities. The ability of a leader to make decisions, the significance of context, timing, objectives, and the relationships among these aspects have all been emphasized more and more as leadership theories have developed.

2.2 ACTUALIZED LEADERSHIP

The second literature that I should be reviewing is William L. Sparks's 2019 book on Actualized Leadership: Meeting Your Shadow and Maximizing Your Potential published by Society For Human Resource Management, Virginia (shrm.org). The author shared that Actualized Leadership offers a synthesised framework based on twenty years of research and inquiry. It is rooted in the fundamental theoretical pillars of such authorities as Jung, Abraham Maslow, Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, David McClelland, and Viktor Frankl. The author described the three positive motivator needs—Achiever, Affirmer, or Asserter—and their corresponding styles, according to the book, each represent a particular person. Each leadership style has a distinctive leadership shadow that corresponds to it, such as the Asserter's Fear of Betrayal, the Achiever's Fear of Failure, and the Affirmer's Fear of Rejection, which frequently leads in poor performance under pressure, if not outright dysfunction. The author reminds that we have a choice: we can choose to meet and process our shadow, or we can choose to ignore or deny it, in which case it will process and govern us.

The author mentioned that Self-awareness is a prerequisite for both personal development and good leadership. We frequently equate self-awareness with recognizing and emphasizing our abilities. The author agreed that we frequently turn to blame others or defending our own limitations when under stress since we typically strive to ignore or deny our bad qualities and natural emotions. Known for saying that most people are destined to live their lives in the "fog of illusion", Swiss psychologist Carl Jung referred to this typical response as the "shadow" and called it the "shadow response."

The author emphasizes that, over the past ten years, a lot has been written about leadership and positive psychology, and many businesses have firmly embraced the idea that we should concentrate on people's strengths rather than their faults. According to these groups, fostering a positive workplace culture inspires everyone to be their best selves. The author pushes over this idea in Actualized Leadership. He contends that one-sided self-awareness results from emphasizing our positive traits while ignoring, denying, or projecting our negative traits. He encourages us to take the time to delve deep into our own, unique motivations.

Leadership Style	Motivation	Description	Leadership Shadow	Shadow Tendencies	Impact on Others
Achiever	Achievement	Organized, Focused, Disciplined, Detail-oriented	Fear of Failure	Narrow-minded, Rigid, Cautious, "Micromanager"	"Detached" Group Culture
Affirmer	Affiliation	Friendly, Warm, Empathetic, Loyal	Fear of Rejection	Anxious, Conflict-avoidant, Naïve, Accommodating	"Dramatic" Group Culture
Asserter	Power	Candid, Decisive, Rational, Strategic	Fear of Betrayal	Controlling, Arrogant, Blunt, Condescending	"Dependent" Group Culture

Table 2 : Actualized Performance Framework (Sparks, 2019)

The author explained that the Actualized Leadership concept is built on determining individual needs related to that individual dominating motive. At this point, the research and the concept bring about interesting finding which would be useful for our research purpose. The author emphasized that our conduct and leadership style are driven by three unique motivator needs: achievement, affiliation, and power. Every motivating need has a unique leadership shadow and behavioural characteristics that indicate a particular leadership style. The Actualized Leadership paradigm is described in general and in detail in Table 2 above. According to the author, the objective, regardless of whether you are an Achiever, Affirmer, or Asserter, is to actualize your style so that you can better manage the frequency and intensity of your leadership shadow. The shadow behaviours for which leadership style is describe in Table 3 below.

Leadership Style	Leadership Shadow	Shadow Behaviors
Achiever	Fear of Failure	Micromanaging; obsessive; rigid; pessimistic; stubborn
Affirmer	Fear of Rejection	Conflict avoidant; devalues own opinions; accommodating
Asserter	Fear of Betrayal	Arrogant; controlling; skeptical; autocratic

Table 3 : Leadership Shadows in the Context of ALP Framework (Sparks, 2019)

With the twenty over years of research, the author does establish some reputation on leadership styles research. The author also created a self-assessment tool for readers. The free assessment (<http://www.ALPSFree.com>) was provided by the author and had encourage readers to take the Actualized leader profile test. You will be led directly to your profile findings after submitting your answers, where you can view a leader-style summary and an estimate of your level of self-actualization at the time. The author also provided the link (<http://www.DrWillSparks.com/ALPoffer>) if you're interested in completing the full Actualized Leader Profile, which includes scores for each of the three motive needs and leader styles, your level of self-actualization right now, and your scores on the 3 Sequences of Self-Actualization as well as the 9 Attributes of Actualized Leaders.

In addition, the author, through its research, found that there are nine characteristics of self-actualized people. These are identified in the Actualized Leadership model, which the author refers to as the "9 Attributes of Actualized Leaders." Three domains 'cognition (how actualized leaders think), emotion (how actualized leaders feel), and behaviour' are used to categorize these nine attributes (what actualized leaders do). To create a "sequence" of self-actualization, one attribute from each of the three domains must be connected. Confidence, Performance, and Renewal are the three steps in the process of self-actualization. These are tabulated in Table 4 below.

Three Sequences of Self-Actualization	COGNITION How Actualized Leaders Think	EMOTION How Actualized Leaders Feel	BEHAVIOR What Actualized Leaders Do
CONFIDENCE	1. OBJECTIVE The degree to which your judgment is based on the facts and is not influenced by personal feelings.	4. COURAGE The degree to which you are willing to do something that frightens you.	7. CANDOR The degree to which you are open, honest, frank, and sincere in your communications with others.
PERFORMANCE	2. HYPERFOCUS The degree to which you consistently engage in an intense form of mental concentration.	5. TRUST The degree to which you are willing to maintain a confident expectation in others.	8. FLOW The degree to which you consistently engage in peak performance.
RENEWAL	3. OPTIMAL TIME ORIENTATION (OTO) The degree to which you have a balanced sense of time and live primarily in the present.	6. ACCEPTANCE The degree to which you totally and completely accept yourself.	9. SOLITUDE The degree to which you are comfortable being alone.

Table 4 : 9 Attributes of Actualized Leaders

The 9 attributes were further elaborated by the authors with example on the application. These application does allow the authors to express the differences through real-life application. In fact, the application does help the reader to understand further on the attributes. The author explained that the three sequences—one for each domain—that are formed by the nine attributes of actualized leaders are linked to the three sequences of self-actualization as well.

Gaining confidence is the first step in developing into a more actualized leader. For them to tackle the difficulties they encounter and carry out their duties well, leaders need to be very self-assured (or self-efficacy). The author agreed that Actualized Leaders frequently radiate quiet confidence that is tinged with humility. 'Bravado and bluster are frequently displayed', especially by Asserters. This activity is frequently used as a form of self-medication for poor self-worth and insecurity. The performance sequence comes after confidence and is the outcome of quiet confidence based on objectivity, courage, and truthfulness.

As displayed by the author, the goal of the performance sequence is to define optimal or peak performance, which is when a person is in the zone and giving their all. This series is based on establishing hyperfocus on the task at hand, having faith in both you and other people, and going with the flow. The final sequence is renewal, which makes sure that we develop long-lasting habits that enable time for rest, refreshment, and contemplation in order to prevent burnout. The author explained that when one has invested all their energy into a project and have gone through the performance process, that is when he is able to renew himself the most. For better or worse, that is when one frequently feels like one deserve some leisure and give themselves permission to fully rest without interruptions or guilt.

To conclude, this literature does bring new insight on the types of leadership styles that were available. The author had spent more than 6 months to collect these data and with over 600 respondents, it would be convincing that these leadership style can be applied to the modern world. However, it is noted that the data collected during the research were from the same organization. The 3 leadership styles, Achiever, Affirmer, and Asserter that the author has researched on would be used as some of the other leadership style for us to research on, which could fit the Millennial and Generation Y expectation.

2.3 AGILE BUSINESS LEADERSHIP METHODS FOR INDUSTRY 4.0

This is the next literature that was reviewed, and it is the 'Agile Business Leadership Methods for Industry 4.0' by Dr. Bulent Akkay. This literature was chosen as the topic mentioned on the current industry era and it could talk about how the leadership manage the employees. The digitization of manufacturing has caused a huge change in how we make goods. As the fourth manufacturing revolution, this transformation has been given the name "Industry 4.0" because it is so intriguing. According to the author, mechanization utilizing water and steam power was a key component of the first and second industrial revolutions. Building on the third industrial revolution's embrace of computers and automation, the fourth will further it with the use of intelligent, autonomous systems that are driven by data and machine learning. Water and steam power were used for mechanization throughout the first and second industrial revolutions. Electricity was used in the second industrial revolution for assembly lines and mass manufacturing. The authors explained that being the change as well as assisting and supporting it are all components of agile leadership. People are inspired by people who lead by example and actively pursue personal development (Schrage, et al., 2016). Gandhi once remarked, "Be the change you wish to see." This is achieved by actions rather than words. As the current digitalized world are running on agile. There are Agile Management, Agile Project Management, etc. And this leadership style strikes out from the earlier known styles as it sensed to have a different way of managing employees. According to Vives (2018), there are nine features of an Agile leader and there are shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 : Nine features of Agile Leadership (Vives, et al., 2018)

According to Vives (2018), employees are given a sense of direction by agile leaders, who frequently convene groups to discuss issues. They aid personnel in thoroughly grasping the vision, identifying the importance of and priorities for the company, reaching difficult decisions, and maintaining goals (Parker et al., 2015). The author agreed that Agile leaders offer their team members the confidence to do their tasks, work together with them, and love the work they do through empowering and motivating them toward shared goals.

The author mentioned about the leadership theories and had explained the four main model, 'trait theory, behavioural theories, contingency theories, and the modern theories'. As agreed by the earlier author mentioned in section 2.1 above, the trait theory contends that leadership is an innate quality in people rather than an acquired attribute. Leaders are distinguished from other people by their innate qualities. As a result, the only way to define the phenomena of leadership is to thoroughly analyse the characteristics of this sort of individual. Unlike the earlier author in section 2.1, this author researched that this notion has been primarily challenged by the observation that sometimes group members with superior traits to the leader do not manifest themselves as leaders. The current circumstance does not fit the characteristic hypothesis. To completely comprehend the leadership phenomenon, it is now required to concentrate on additional factors in addition to the characteristics described above. Another issue with this theory was how difficult it was to measure the traits of a leader and how some specific traits were seen differently than they were.

The author also explained about both the behavioural and the contingency theories, which is similar to the earlier literature, as discussed in section 2.1. The term "behavioural approach" refers to the actions taken by a leader while exercising leadership in particular circumstances. The author had researched that studies had been conducted by universities and all had the same outcome that people-oriented leaders demonstrate traits like caring for others, being sensitive to their feelings, and considering their wants and preferences. On the other side, executives who put their attention on the business exhibit actions geared toward completing the assigned work or reaching the established objective. Also in the contingency theories, the author agreed that different situations required different leadership styles.

The pace of change in the world order has been increased by globalization, and many inventions have entered our daily lives (Aslam, Eugster, Ho, Jaumotte & Piazza, et al., 2018). In this setting, there has been a noteworthy evolution in the idea of leadership, and leaders in enterprises are starting to be accorded more weight. The author agreed that new leadership theories have taken the role of traditional leadership theories, which fall short in explaining leadership concepts and behaviours. On the other hand, the author claims that Industry 4.0, which is based on a higher level of creative ability, calls for participative management, organizational flexibility, a type of leadership that is based on the desires and needs of individuals, supporting individuals, emphasizing merit and ethical behaviour, constantly increasing knowledge, and putting science into practice. The modern leadership styles to use in managing personnel from the millennial generation would be those.

The author explained that the definition of transactional leadership is a style of leadership in which the leader communicates his expectations to his followers in a straightforward manner and outlines the rewards they can expect in exchange for their expected performance and effort. The tasks that employees are expected to complete, the standards of performance that are expected of them, their bosses' obedience, and the rewards they will receive when they succeed are all clearly outlined in transactional leadership (Lee et al., 2020). Also, according to the author, providing praise for a job well done and enhancing pay or promoting subordinates are two different methods business leaders can reward their followers to increase efficiency. Among the various tasks that transactional leaders can effectively do are enhancing organizational effectiveness, reducing unnecessary risks, reaching goals and objectives, and boosting employee motivation (Lee et al., 2020).

Another leadership styles that is popular, is the transformational leadership styles. The author explained that to achieve the mission and goals of the company, transformational leadership involves changing the attitudes and actions of the organization's members. The author agreed that the complimentary nature of the two leadership styles—transactional and transformational—is reflected in both. Transformative leadership guarantees that the objectives are met through altering

the members of the group's ethical standards, behaviour, and motives (Lee et al., 2020). Transactional leadership enables both sides to achieve their goals by economic, political, or psychological means (Lee et al., 2020). The author further explained that a transformative leader cares about the growth of their followers on a personal level. They assess if followers have the capacity to carry out their current responsibilities and assume more in the future. They provide specific tasks or examples to suit organizational goals while also greatly enhancing the skills and drive of the followers. For their followers to expose and use their knowledge and talents effectively, transformational leaders set the right conditions for them to do so. They also support their followers' creativity by giving them the freedom to come up with new ideas and approaches (Lee et al., 2020).

As shown in Figure 1 below, another leadership styles that the author researched on is the Technological Leadership. According to the author, the technological leader paves the way for others to successfully use, manage, assess, and comprehend the technologies that make up the planned world. Our complex, global society is becoming more and more reliant on technology, making the technological leader essential. The technology leader can contribute to driving technological growth in his circumstances and make well-informed and respected decisions (John B et al., 2019). Creating a technology leadership team, assessing professional development methods, technical requirements, employee learning and performance, and effectively addressing cybersecurity are all things that managers who want to lead staff members with technology might benefit from doing (John B et al., 2019).

To put it another way, managers who have embraced the concept of technological leadership should establish the organization's technology goals and vision, lead the technology, set a good example for their staff, provide the resources required to encourage and support the use of technology in the organization, implement professional development activities, and make sure that technology is integrated into the organization (Lee et al., 2020). According to the author, if a leader does not see the value in technology, he cannot implement it into his company or ensure that his employees will benefit from it. To increase the company's performance, identify the technical tools needed for those tasks, and guarantee that technology is incorporated into the organization, the leader must first grasp the importance and advantages of technology for the organization (John B et al., 2019).

According to the author, there is some difference between Strategic Leadership and Visionary Leadership. The author mentioned that four leadership qualities are necessary for managers who use a strategic leadership approach: managerial (ensuring organizational order), political (ability to comprehend employees, manage, and direct the employees to achieve specific goals and objectives), transformational (paying attention to employees' opinions and motivating them), and ethical (expressing commitment to corporate values)'. A manager will have the chance to succeed in

unpredictable situations if they possess the strategic leadership traits (Lee et al., 2020). Closely explained by the author is that the capacity to invent is another definition of visionary leadership. High levels of organizational harmony are provided by visionary leaders who inspire and motivate employees and define the organization's vision and objective. Moreover, they boost trust, performance, and job loyalty (Taylor et al., 2013). Visionary leaders are those that make plans that will help the organization succeed with the help of the employees and who put out a lot of effort to get there. They also inspire high levels of employee motivation and maximize staff performance.

Figure 2 : Six Leadership Styles (Akkaya, 2020)

In conclusion, the author had explained on the type of leadership styles which give insight on how these leadership could help the organization in the concept of Industry 4.0. Although, there is little emphasise on the motivation of the employees, some of the leadership styles could be used on our research if they fit in to the new generation employees.

2.4 MILLENNIAL GENERATION AND GENERATION Z

One's direction, enthusiasm, perseverance, and persistence in pursuing a goal are greatly influenced by their level of motivation (Shashi, Ajay & Kiran, et al., 2012). Employee commitment and job happiness depend on their drive to work (Claypool K.K., et al., 2017). Employee commitment to the company increases when they are happy, which in turn helps the business to become more successful and productive (Claypool K.K., et al., 2017). Employees that are driven and committed are aware of the organization's ideals and objectives, and they frequently care about its success and future growth (Shashi, Ajay & Kiran, et al., 2012). Hence, the effectiveness of the workforce has a significant impact on the organization's success. Employee effectiveness and commitment are frequently affected by factors including job overload, unclear goals, shifting corporate priorities, and other similar occurrences (Claypool K.K., et al., 2017). It might not be true to presume that the same leadership qualities that inspired older generations will inspire employees from the Millennial Generation and Generation Z. Research on the leadership styles that inspire employees from these two ages group is limited.

In this section, two articles should be reviewed as both talks about the motivation of both the Millennial and the Generation Z. For referencing, below is the acronym used for the two articles.

Acronym	Article
MLR 1	Intrinsic motivation of millennials and generation Z in the new post-pandemic reality (2022)
MLR 2	What Motivates Millennials and Generation Z? An investigation into the motivation and associated rewards which impact the two generational age cohorts; Millennials and Gen Z (2017).

Table 5 : Acronym of Articles

Employers need to be prepared for the Generation Z, according to both papers, who are only recently entering the workforce. Although Generation Z and the Millennial Generation share many traits, Generation Z also exhibits several novel behavioural characteristics. Today's managers need to understand not just the best practices for dealing with young, inexperienced employees but also the distinctive characteristics of the generation that have been shaped by their experiences (Guzman, et al., 2022). Regarding the culture and technologies of the younger age, every generation harbours some reservations (Segal, et al., 2022). As a varied and cosmopolitan generation, Generation Z is known for its casual communication style, which is both direct and impatient (Schroth, 2019). In line with the Millennial generation, which is likewise renowned for being impatient and perhaps having unreasonable expectations (Aruna & Anitha, et al., 2015).

According to MLR2, Generation Z heavy reliance on technology and the internet is mostly to blame for their exceedingly low patience and shortening attention span. Moreover, they are typically connected with qualities such as individualism, materialism, as well as very egocentric, and astute (Schroth, 2019). Also, Generation Z members are expected to be online constantly to network and communicate, which is why they are regarded as the generation with the highest level of connectivity (Segal, et al., 2022). However, they could readily exploit their strengths, including their high levels of alertness, entrepreneurship, toleration, and integrity, in both the workplace and in daily life. Taking advantage of the information online, they tend to be resourceful, efficiency and possible innovation. The distinct different between the two generation, in term of working together, as both articles agreed, that 'Millennial value teamwork' while Generation Z 'prefer to work independently' (Larkin, et al., 2017:25). According to MLR1, Millennial generation anticipate that before they prove themselves, their ideas and opinions will be respected in the same way as those of a more experienced worker The capacity of the Millennial generation to identify and comprehend why some components of their employment are constrained by their degree of expertise is one area where they face challenges (Aruna & Anitha, et al., 2015).

According to MLR1's author, extrinsic and intrinsic motivators can both be present in the workplace. In addition to the need for recognition and performance, intrinsic motivators are incentives connected to the task itself. As explained by the author, financial incentives, the work atmosphere, and the manager's leadership style are examples of extrinsic motivators. Also, as discussed by MLR2's author, Generation Z is driven to find a job that respects their autonomy and privacy while also enabling them to strike a work-life balance. Generation Z is more inclined to apply for jobs and positions that match their interests, offer chances for growth personally and professionally, and are connected to those interests (Guzman, et al., 2022). They are not interested in holding jobs that would merely serve to satisfy the needs of their employers and superiors as compared to the Millennial (Larkin, et al., 2017).

When Generation Z job seekers are looking and applying for a job, extrinsic benefits like monetary remuneration are no longer the main criteria. Alternatively, they are more intrinsically motivated, which means that they are more drawn to fulfilment from within, self-actualization, and continued development and growth (Larkin, et al., 2017). Even though they place a high importance on responsibility and getting things done, both at work and in their personal lives, these people also want others to recognise their accomplishments and regard them as people (Guzman, et al., 2022). Such an environment would not only boost their levels of motivation the greatest, but it would also have a positive effect on their mental stability and sense of fulfilment (Segal, et al., 2022). Both authors also agreed that the delayed or long-term reward system is not appealing to the Millennial generation (Aruna & Anitha, 2015). Millennial anticipate receiving their financial rewards right away and expecting their earnings to rise throughout the course of their early careers (Aruna & Anitha,

2015). Because of the Millennial generation's mentality, businesses frequently find themselves having to offer them competitive salary packages to keep them (Aruna & Anitha, 2015).

Both authors agreed that, in another aspects of findings, that compared to the Millennial generation, Generation Z has lesser expectations and less self-confidence. They are consequently more concerned with safety in a variety of spheres of life. Having a secure life free of unforeseen and unwelcome changes outside of work, according to MLR1, is one of the most sought workplace and achievement incentives. Such anxiety could be attributed to the recessionary time they went through when they were younger, as well as the effects that time had on their parents (Segal, et al., 2022).

In terms of Generation Z's work ethic, MLR1's author contends that, despite their current level and position at work, they value maintaining their privacy as well as being independent and self-reliant. MLR2's author agreed that they also expect workplace transparency and expect to be kept informed rather than neglected. In a similar vein, they desire that, despite their youth, their supervisors respect their opinions and are approachable and open to them (Larkin, et al., 2017). When it comes to various chances and difficulties at work, they are seen as being quite versatile. Both authors agreed that their participation in various tasks is a means for them to demonstrate their desire to work hard and establish themselves, and as a result, they anticipate recognition and appreciation.

Finally, they want their place of employment to be a stimulating environment where their creativity will not be silent (Guzman, et al., 2022). Hence, it is necessary that managers give them projects that will foster both a nice work environment and a competitive spirit. Generation Z may lack interpersonal skills because they have grown up with less face-to-face connection; therefore, it is vital for leaders and managers to help them learn how to communicate appropriately in social situations (Segal, et al., 2022). So, employers need to be aware of those characteristics of Generation Z. Ignoring such distinctive characteristics of Generation Z could result in decreased engagement and productivity (Segal, et al., 2022).

Similarly, according to MLR2, the Millennial generation demands a healthy work-life balance, while the X generation and baby boomers think that success at work is related to the amount of time spent working (Aruna & Anitha, 2015). Long office hours and a more serious, formal tone were characteristics of the working environment in the past (Aruna & Anitha, 2015). Millennial employees are drawn to more relaxed workplaces with plenty of technology and a more laid-back ambience that encourages having fun at work (Aruna & Anitha, 2015). They anticipate having the freedom to work remotely part- or full-time because of technology advancements that make it possible to do so (Guzman, et al., 2022).

According to MLR1, the perception of Millennial is that they are approachable, open-minded, smart, responsible, socially conscious, well-informed, and civically engaged (Aruna & Anitha, et al., 2015).

Some depict Millennial as arguably the best employees in the sectors today because they believe they are constantly trying to do what is best in the situation (Clemons, et al., 2014). The Millennial generation has a stronger commitment to their work than to the company they work for (Aruna & Anitha, 2015). Many Millennials think they have enough job experience to handle manager-level responsibilities based on their schooling and internships (Aruna & Anitha, et al., 2015). Also, they are self-assured and at ease disputing management decisions, frequently asking to be included in the decision-making process (Aruna & Anitha, 2015). It is not surprising that the Millennial generation is more culturally sensitive given that they are the most diverse generation (Clemons, et al., 2014). People need to go past preconceptions in the Millennial workforce since it has been there long enough and developed enough to see if their contributions are beneficial or detrimental (Aruna & Anitha, et al., 2015).

An issue that older generation leaders are facing is their perception of the disrespect that Millennial employees have for their superiors (FerriReed, et al., 2014). The Millennial generation was brought up and taught using a more relationship-based strategy, which these leaders struggle to grasp. The connection to parents and instructors was frequently one of friendship rather than one of superior and subordinate, in contrast to how the previous generation was reared by parents and educated by teachers adopting a more authoritarian and dictatorial method (FerriReed, et al., 2014). So, they are not disrespectful to superiors in the way they treat them. Instead, it's exactly how Millennial employees have been instructed to interact with managers (FerriReed, et al., 2014).

In term of leadership, both authors agreed that the concept of management is now viewed by Generation Z as being connected to mechanical operations like controlling and constantly evaluating how well a corporation performs. The Millennial generation value honesty and integrity as well as intellect, dexterity, and self-control (Aruna & Anitha, et al., 2015). The same author is of the opinion that Generation Z does not value creativity and imagination as highly as Millennial generations did as leadership qualities. Instead, they will appreciate where leaders will respect them despite their inexperience and inexperienced age, pay attention to their thoughts, and take their perspectives into consideration (Aruna & Anitha, et al., 2015). Furthermore, they think that the workplace ought to emphasize creative thinking and individual effort. If a manager had a positive outlook and tried to give staff members opportunity for internal growth, Generation Z would be the most content in their work environment (FerriReed, et al., 2014). Like the Millennial generation, they place a premium on soft skills and look for emotionally intelligent leaders with strong communication abilities that support a positive and inclusive workplace culture and are able to provide the required mentorship at work (FerriReed, et al., 2014).

2.5 RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

As shown in Figure 3 below, the study model is created to examine potential leadership styles that leaders may use to inspire or affect the morale of Millennial and Generation Z employees, the country's future workforce. The investigated leadership styles are represented as the X independent variable while the motivation of the Millennial and Generation Z employee as the Y dependent variable.

Figure 3 : Research Model on Leadership Styles for Millennial & Generation Z Employee

From the RQ and RO, the following hypotheses need to be investigated.

Hypothesis 1 (H1): The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Transformational Leadership.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Team Leadership.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Actualized Leadership.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Agile Leadership.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

The terms quantitative, qualitative, and mixed approaches were defined by Christensen, Johnson, & Turner (2019) as three distinct study design methodologies. Based on the topic and issue being addressed in the study, prior personal experience, and the intended audience, each writer has the option to choose one of these three writing styles (Christensen, Johnson, & Turner, 2019). While qualitative methods are used to learn about and comprehend human behaviour and evaluate the link between non-numerical variables, quantitative methods focus primarily on numerical values and data collecting with the purpose of statistically testing a theory (Christensen, Johnson, & Turner, 2019). When a single research design is insufficient for the study, a mixed methods approach is utilized, which incorporates both qualitative and quantitative approaches to address the problem and test hypotheses (Borgstede and Scholz, 2021).

Quantitative Methods	Mixed Methods	Qualitative Methods
Pre-determined	Both predetermined and emerging methods	Emerging methods
Instrument based questions	Both open- and closed-ended questions	Open-ended questions
Performance data, attitude data, observational data, and census data	Multiple forms of data drawing on all possibilities	Interview data, observation data, document data, and audiovisual data
Statistical analysis	Statistical and text analysis	Text and image analysis
Statistical interpretation	Across databases interpretation	Themes, patterns interpretation

Table 6 : Quantitative, Mixed, and Qualitative Methods (Christensen, Johnson, & Turner, 2019).

3.1 RESEARCH APPROACH

According to Grover (2015), the approach to research contains philosophical assumptions as well as unique methodologies or processes, which are two key elements in any description. A plan or proposal for doing research that combines specific techniques, study designs, and philosophical viewpoints is known as a broad wide research strategy (Grover, 2015). Figure 4 below depicts the paradigm employ to describe how these three elements interact with one another. While designing a study, researchers must consider their underlying philosophical worldview assumptions, the research design that is based on those assumptions, and the specific research methodologies or procedures that put the approach into action (Patel and Patel, 2019).

Figure 4 : Framework for Research (Grover, 2015).

According to Borgstede and Scholz (2021), category creation is the main method of analysis used in qualitative research. By developing descriptive systems for empirical phenomena, it is possible to carry out a more thorough investigation of the underlying empirical structure. To interpret the observations, a conceptual framework of categories (or sorts) is established (Borgstede and Scholz, 2021). Despite the many research methods utilized by different qualitative methodologies, most strategies are formally based on some type of classification of samples that have certain comparable qualities (Borgstede and Scholz, 2021).

According to Yadav (2022), It is challenging to define what makes qualitative research of high quality. Several methods that are used in qualitative research are based on different philosophical positions. The challenge of regulating the metrics used to gauge the quality of research is not new to qualitative researchers. Particularly, when the ideal objectivity, reliability, and validity is not met (Tomaszewski, Zarestky, & Gonzalez, 2020). Sometimes qualitative research is judged using the standards of quantitative research. Yadav (2022) asserts that scientifically grounded experimental research is the dominant paradigm in educational research. The value and application of qualitative research may be diminished by failing to consider the significance of a harmonizing match for purpose on the research paradigm, the researcher's perspective on the technique they employ, and hypotheses and conjectures regarding the dominance of quantitative research (Yadav, 2022).

Even though Quantitative research is the most popular research methodology, it does have some limitations because the question cannot be changed even if the participant does not comprehend it. According to Fournier (2020), there is a standard procedure to follow while beginning this study approach. The primary justification for using such a design approach is its focus on theory testing and hypothesis testing, which enables the potential to acquire relevant understanding on both the Millennial Generation and the Generation Z workforce's drive to work and accomplish corporate goals when led by various leadership philosophies at the workplace.

When used for psychological studies, this research style might be difficult to employ. Even though surveys and questionnaires are used to collect data, the hypothesis should be as short and straightforward as feasible to allow the question that results to be seen as such (Borgstede and Scholz, 2021). Using the results of this quantitative study, it is aimed to pinpoint which leadership philosophies effectively inspire employees from the Millennial Generation and the Generation Z. By doing this, managers may be better prepared to promote increased employee performance and productivity.

The research strategy that tends to be quantitative, qualitative, or mixed is influenced by worldviews, designs, and methodologies (Grover, 2015). Table 7 presents the differences that would be helpful.

Tend to or Typically ...	Qualitative Approaches	Quantitative Approaches	Mixed Methods Approaches
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use these philosophical assumptions Employ these strategies of inquiry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constructivist/ transformative knowledge claims Phenomenology, grounded theory, ethnography, case study, and narrative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Postpositivist knowledge claims Surveys and experiments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pragmatic knowledge claims Sequential, concurrent, and transformative
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Employ these methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open-ended questions, emerging approaches, text or image data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Closed-ended questions, predetermined approaches, numeric data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Both open- and closed-ended questions, both emerging and predetermined approaches, and both quantitative and qualitative data and analysis
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use these practices of research as the researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Positions him- or herself Collects participant meanings Focuses on a single concept or phenomenon Brings personal values into the study Studies the context or setting of participants Validates the accuracy of findings Makes interpretations of the data Creates an agenda for change or reform Collaborates with the participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tests or verifies theories or explanations Identifies variables to study Relates variables in questions or hypotheses Uses standards of validity and reliability Observes and measures information numerically Uses unbiased approaches Employs statistical procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collects both quantitative and qualitative data Develops a rationale for mixing Integrates the data at different stages of inquiry Presents visual pictures of the procedures in the study Employs the practices of both qualitative and quantitative research

Table 7 : Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods (Patel and Patel, 2019; Grover, 2015).

3.2 RESEARCH METHODS

According to Taherdoost (2022), In quantitative research, the phenomena that the observations can reflect on are described and explained using numerical values generated from the data. This strategy makes use of both procedures and descriptive empirical assertions that explain the instances' actual meaning rather than what they "ought" to signify. (Taherdoost, 2022). It also employs empirical analysis to determine the degree to which a certain policy or program satisfies a norm or standard. (Grover, 2015). The collected numerical data is then examined using mathematical procedures. Also, a description of a subject is supposed to be provided through both qualitative and quantitative research approaches. The contrast, however, is found in the definition's final phrase, which focuses on various sorts of analytical methodologies, including the use of mathematics and statistics in quantitative research (Patel and Patel, 2019). In numerous disciplines, including education, psychology, physics, biology, and the natural sciences, among others, quantitative research tries to define a given occurrence by gathering numerical data to address specific questions like how many and what proportion (Taherdoost, 2022).

The process of collecting data makes use of tools that are specifically designed to record quantitative data. There are a variety of strategies to use while gathering data, such as conducting surveys of individuals and employing experimental methods. (Taherdoost, 2022). To provide an accurate measuring opportunity and deliver quantitative data that is correct, the devices must be arranged and evaluated (Patel and Patel, 2019). Online platforms, Google Forms will be employed for the present study's data collecting. With today's technology, internet platforms can assist in expanding participation and not only limiting it to a few major corporations (Taherdoost, 2022). Social media platforms are another choice for data collecting because they may reach more people and provide a huge sample size. This results in quick information gathering and gives more time for subsequent analysis (Borgstede and Scholz, 2021). Using the survey approach, we would gather information to investigate what types of leadership inspire employees from both the Millennial and Generation Z age.

The gathered data should be statistically investigated using a variety of quantitative analysis techniques, such as descriptive analysis, explanatory analysis, and inferential types. The process of data analysis often aims to find statistical relationships between the variables (Christensen, Johnson, & Turner, 2019). An evaluation of the constructs and statistics is done after the process steps as part of the validity step (Taherdoost, 2022).

3.3 QUESTIONNAIRE FORMULATION

According to Roopa and Rani (2012), the questionnaire was created in the latter part of the 1800s. Every survey starts with a questionnaire, and a questionnaire's design affects how well it performs. The primary method used to gather quantitative primary data is a questionnaire. (Taherdoost1, 2022). According to Roopa and Rani (2012), to gather quantitative data for analysis in a dependable, repeatable, logical manner, and with internal consistency, a questionnaire is necessary. Every questionnaire must have a distinct purpose that relates to the study's goals, and it must be made clear up front how the information will be utilized (Julian, Annelies, Bruch, & Wolf, 2022). To collect information that is pertinent and helpful, much thought must go into the questionnaire's design. (Roopa and Rani, 2012). A well-designed questionnaire requires thought and effort, and it must be planned out and improved through numerous stages, as shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5 : Phases of creating a questionnaire (Roopa and Rani, 2012).

According to Taherdoost1 (2022), questionnaires might be of two generally relevant sorts or a mixture of those types. These categories include both structured and unstructured questionnaires, and the combination is referred to as quasi-structured. Using sequence questions, the first one follows a specific and distinct pattern. Most data collecting procedures employ them since they are pre-coded. Because they are simple to administer and cover fewer variations, they have several advantages. Moreover, replies are more consistent, which simplifies data administration (Roopa and Rani, 2012). Open-ended inquiries and opinion-types, on the other hand, are used by unstructured kinds. Focus-group interviews are where these sorts work best. The responses have a wide range of options, and it would be difficult to pre-code them all (Taherdoost1, 2022). Using structured type for the majority of the questions, a quasi-type questionnaire also uses some unstructured questions. Answers that are impossible to count are totally excluded (Julian, Annelies, Bruch, & Wolf, 2022).

While reviewing the stages involved in creating a questionnaire, these two primary categories are outlined in greater depth (Taherdoost1, 2022).

3.4 QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

Survey research questionnaires should be easy to understand and well-designed. According to Sreejesk (2014), it is best to avoid using solely capital (upper case) letters because this style is difficult to read. There should be a clear subject grouping and numbering of the questions. To make the questionnaire simpler to complete, clear instructions should be provided. Headings should also be added (Sreejesh, Mohapatra, & Anusree, 2014). According to Julian (2022), the researcher needs to consider the format of the questions, steering clear of "two or more questions in one", such as "Would you be satisfied with your personal Doctor and the Doctors in general?"), questions with two negative answers, and questions that are misleading or ambiguous. There are two types of questions: open (in which the responder develops the response) and closed (when pre-coded response possibilities, such as in multiple-choice questions, are provided (Kelley, Clark, Brown, & Sitzia, 2003).

According to Kelley (2003), the best subjects for closed questions with pre-coded response possibilities are those with known potential answers. It takes little time to administer closed-ended questions, and they are simple to code and analyze. Where feasible, utilize open questions when the number of possible answers is either too great or unknown to pre-code added (Sreejesh, Mohapatra, & Anusree, 2014).

Through the literature review, considering the linkage of the question to the literature and to answer the Research Questions, 25 questions assessment will be generated, along with 8 questions on demographic profiling. The 5-point Likert scale is used with the following scale: "Strongly Disagree" is represented by a score of 1, "Disagree" by a score of 2, "Neither Agree nor Disagree" is represented by a score of 3, "Agree" by a score of 4, and "Strongly Agree" by a score of 5. Table below denotes the different sections of the questionnaire.

Section A was on the respondent's demographic profile. The respondent required to input their gender, age, citizenship, education, designation at work, years of service, industry and staff strength of the current company. The main data required is the age as the research is on the Millennial (26 to 41 years old) and Generation Z age group (10 to 25). The details are coded for ease in the data processing purpose. The Age will be arranged into five categories, with age 10 to 25 years old under code 1, 26 to 41 years old as code 2, 42 to 57 years old as code 3, 58 to 70 years old as code 4.

A1 – Age

A1.1 – 10 to 25 years old

A1.2 – 26 to 41 years old

A1.3 – 42 to 57 years old

A1.4 – 58 to 70 years old

A2 – Gender (Male / Female)

A3 – Citizenship

A4 – Education level

A5 – Designation at work

A6 – Years of Service

A7 - Industry

A8 – Company Staff Strength

Section B, Transformational Leadership. There were 5 traits of transformational leadership selected from the article ‘Leadership, Communication, And Social Influence: A Theory OF Resonance, Activation, And Cultivation’ by Ruben and Gigliotti (2019), to investigate the extent the employees were appreciate these leaders. The five questions will start with “*I am motivated at work if my manager...*” as shown in Table 8 below.

Section C, Team Leadership. There were 5 traits of team leadership selected to investigate the extent the employees were appreciate these leaders. The five questions will start with “*I am motivated at work if my manager...*” as shown in Table 8 below.

Section D, Actualised Leadership. There were 5 traits of actualised leadership selected to investigate the extent the employees were appreciate these leaders. The five questions will start with “*I am motivated at work if my manager...*” as shown in Table 9 below.

Section E, Agile Leadership. There were 5 traits of agile leadership selected to investigate the extent the employees were appreciate these leaders. The five questions will start with “*I am motivated at work if my manager...*” as shown in Table 9 below.

No	Construct	Hypothesis	IV	DV	Questions
1	Transformational Leadership	<p>The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Transformational Leadership.</p> <p>H10: Leadership traits that adhere to the Transformational Leadership style do not positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.</p> <p>H11: Leadership traits that adhere to the Transformational Leadership style do positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.</p>	Transformational Leadership Style	Motivation	B1 – Is open to innovation.
					B2 – Always listen and easy to communicate.
					B3 – believes that each team member may determine their own path to success.
					B4 – use values as guiding frameworks to aid individuals in making decisions and selecting amongst options.
					B5 – mentor and nurture us to learn and grow.
2	Team Leadership	<p>The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Team Leadership.</p> <p>H20: Leadership traits that adhere to the Team Leadership style do not positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.</p> <p>H21: Leadership traits that adhere to the Team Leadership style do positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.</p>	Team Leadership Style	Motivation	C1 – prefer 'private' communication.
					C2 – encourage individual contribution and less co-operation between employees.
					C3 – Need longer duration to decide on work activities.
					C4 – is not accountable for the team's accomplishments and mistakes.
					C5 – depend on individual to motivate themselves and create passion of their work.

Table 8 : Survey Questions Formulation

No	Construct	Hypothesis	IV	DV	Questions
3	Actualized Leadership	<p>The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Actualized Leadership.</p> <p>H30: Leadership traits that adhere to the Actualized Leadership style do positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.</p> <p>H31: Leadership traits that adhere to the Actualized Leadership style do not positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.</p>	Actualized Leadership Style	Motivation	D1 – show concerned over their own concerns and less concerned with other issues.
					D2 – like to work on complicated issues.
					D3 – check on individual status (education, political beliefs, race, or color) before befriending anyone.
					D4 – is serious to work with.
					D5 – promote team activities.
4	Agile Leadership	<p>The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Agile Leadership.</p> <p>H40: Leadership traits that adhere to the Agile Leadership style do not positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.</p> <p>H41: Leadership traits that adhere to the Agile Leadership style do positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.</p>	Actualized Leadership Style	Motivation	E1 – promote continuous learning.
					E2 – encourage feedback and useful criticism.
					E3 – encourage cross-functional collaboration.
					E4 – do not micromanage.
					E5 – accept changes and adapt the change quickly.

Table 9 : Survey Questions Formulation (cont')

Section F, Motivation Factors. There were 5 motivation factors selected to investigate the extent the employees would be motivated if these are presented. The following five questions were used.

F1 – I am satisfied and motivated with the current salary.

F2 – I am motivated if there is incentive or variable bonus program.

F3 – I am motivated with recognition/appreciation from my boss.

F4 – I am motivated with enjoyment from my tasks and responsibilities.

F5 – ‘Work from Home’ is a must.

Section B to E would be used to determine which leadership was preferred by the Millennial and Generation Z employees. As for section F, the results could help in determining If the earlier research is still applicable and if it could apply to the younger generation workforce.

The questionnaire is intended to answer the study appropriate objectives and questions while also evaluate the hypotheses as shown in Table 10 below.

Related Sections	Research Objectives	Research Questions	Hypothesis
A, B, C	RO1 - To identify the leadership style to manage Millennial and Generation Z employee.	RQ1 - Is transformational leader style preferred by the Millennial and Generation Z employees?	H1 - The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Transformational Leadership. H2 - The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Team Leadership.
A, D, E	RO2 - To identify the modern leadership style to manage Millennial and Generation Z employee.	RQ2 - Is Agile or Actualized leadership style preferred by the Millennial and Generation Z employees?	H3 - The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Actualized Leadership. H4 - The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Agile Leadership.
A, F	RO3 - To discover the motivation factor for Millennial and Generation Z employees	RQ3 - What are the motivation factors for Millennial and Generation Z employees?	H1 - H4

Table 10 : Corresponding Research Objectives, Questions, and the Hypotheses

3.5 TARGET AUDIENCE AND DATA COLLECTION

A collection of people who share interests, demographics, and behavioural patterns is known as a target audience (Kelley, Clark, Brown, & Sitzia, 2003). According to Taherdoost (2022), you won't be able to fix issues by gathering comments from arbitrary individuals who have no interest in or expertise of the research topic. The correct people must be targeted for your study if you hope to acquire insightful information (Roopa and Rani, 2012). Building your research plan must include analysing your target audience.

For the current research, the participants should be from the Millennial and Generation Z age group. For the Millennial, these are born in the years of 1981 to 1996 and they would be at the age of 26 to 41 years old respectively by 2022. The survey would be sent to MNC company as well as local private company to have a good sampling of working adults. As for the Generation Z, these are born in the 1997 to 2013 and they would be at the age of 10 to 25 years old by 2022. For these working adults, we would need from those that just stepping into the working environment. The survey would be sent to local university Alumni (year 2017 to 2021). Also, with the help of the Generation X employees, their children, who would be the Generation Z age group, the survey would be sent to them as well.

3.6 SURVEY PILOT TESTING

It is important to evaluate research tools on a pilot sample of the intended audience. According to Taherdoost (2022), although the number of participants is flexible, often between 15 and 30 responders are sufficient. The participants in this stage should also be selected such that they have backgrounds, educational levels, interests, attitudes, and degrees of topic familiarity that are comparable to those of the primary target groups (Taherdoost, 2022). This method will enable the researcher to determine if respondents understand the instructions and the questions, and whether the questions are understood by every responder (Christensen, Johnson, & Turner, 2019). Piloting will reveal whether there are enough response possibilities and whether any questions are routinely disregarded by respondents when closed questions are used (Julian, Annelies, Bruch, & Wolf, 2022). By conducting a pilot, the same procedure that will be utilized in the main survey should be used to detect potential difficulties, such as low response rates.

For this research, we have invited 20 test respondents from different age groups and industries. The pilot test lasted for 5 days and with specific comments from these group of respondents to improve the survey questionnaire.

Using the Cronbach's Alpha Calculation on this answered survey, as shown in Table 11 below, the response on the Team Leadership style questions is 'Unacceptable'. Further interview with these respondents and had noted the confusion on question 5 of the survey. It was phrased as "we have passion in our work through motivation", which have confused the respondents on passion of work or motivation. The revised question is now 'depend on individual to motivate themselves and create passion of their work'.

Survey	Cronbach's Alpha Score	Internal Consistency
Transformational Leadership Style	0.857	Good
Team Leadership Style	0.242	Unacceptable
Actualized Leadership Style	0.850	Good
Agile Leadership Style	0.820	Good
Motivational factors	0.912	Good

Table 11: Cronbach's Alpha Score for Piloting Test on Survey Questions

3.7 DATA ANALYSIS PLAN

All analyses have the same goal: to condense data into a form that can be easily comprehended and that offers the answers to our initial inquiries (Abulela & Harwell, 2020). To do this, researchers must closely scrutinize their data; they should develop a close relationship with their data (Taherdoost, 2022). When data analysis is rushed, important data details may be missed, and occasionally the wrong analyses are performed, leading to inaccurate findings and misleading conclusions (Abulela & Harwell, 2020). Nevertheless, it cannot be emphasized enough, Data dredging is a strategy that should be avoided by researchers, especially in investigations where many dependent variables may be linked to several independent factors. (Taherdoost, 2022). Testing at this level of significance will still produce a high percentage of false positive results in datasets with few true links because P 0.05's assessment of many potential associations in a dataset will make one in 20 relationships appear to be "statistically significant" (Abulela & Harwell, 2020).

The survey's design will determine the method of data analysis, which should have been carefully considered throughout the survey's planning stages (Taherdoost, 2022). When analysing data obtained through qualitative methods, it is recommended to apply tried-and-true methods like content analysis. When quantitative methods have been used, relevant statistical tests can be run. (Ali, 2021).

According to Ali (2021), two major benefits typically accompany the quantitative approach to a phenomenon. At the beginning, it gives researchers the ability to orderly group, summarize, and present their findings. Descriptive statistics is the umbrella term for all these mechanisms and methods (Abulela & Harwell, 2020). Furthermore, it permits a researcher to comprehend and make judgments on a phenomenon (a sample) that is investigated in a specific, limited group. (Ali, 2021). Ali (2021) also described that to allow the resulting findings to be applied to the entire population, the sample is always systematically drawn from a much larger group. Inductive reasoning is the method by which a researcher comes to the conclusions; to put it another way, this technique prepares the ground for that process. Inferential statistics are used to quantify each step of the process as well as the methods, results, and conclusions (Ali, 2021). To analyse the gathered data, descriptive and inferential statistics would be employed..

According to Pandis (2016), when utilizing a crosstabulation, the Chi-Square statistic is employed to assess 'Tests of Independence' (also known as a bivariate table). When 'two categorical variables' are presented in a crosstabulation, the intersections of the categories of the two variables are displayed in the table's cells (Pandis, 2016). According to Rana and Singhal (2015), the "Test of Independence" compares the observed pattern of cell responses to the pattern that would be predicted if the two factors were independent of one another to ascertain if there is a link between the two variables. By computing the Chi-Square statistic and comparing it to a critical value from the Chi-Square distribution, the researcher may establish if the observed cell counts significantly differ from the expected cell counts (Pandis, 2016). The Chi-Square analysis will be applied to the current study to determine the variables independence.

3.8 ETHICAL ISSUE

Research involving human subjects must be regulated, as has been demonstrated by unethical research in the past (Roopa and Rani, 2012). When conducting this research, we will adhere strictly to the moral and professional standards set out by the University of Roehampton and the Personal Data Protection Act (PDPA) of Singapore. We had incorporated sufficient information about the study aims, participation requirements, and acknowledgement of permission into the questionnaire design and made it available on the web-based survey's home page. As the survey won't collect respondents' personal information like name, business name, email address, or network location, they were guaranteed that their identity will remain anonymous. Only demographic data, including gender, age group, and job title, will be gathered for the purposes of data analysis. Moreover, they are given the assurance that their answers would be kept internal to the school for academic use only and not disclosed to outside parties. The study was voluntary, according to the permission form. At any moment, the participant has the option to withdraw. The study's findings are available to the public, even though there are no details of the participants' names.

4. RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION OF FINDINGS

According to Pandis (2016), by making our assumptions and decisions about the structure of our models, the analysis of the data, and the interpretation of our conclusions open and explicit, theory-driven analysis improves the quality of research. According to Rana and Singhal (2015), going back and forth between our theory and data analysis may also aid in our ability to comprehend our study in more depth. In this section, the data analysis was carried out using Microsoft Excel for the 214 responds received in a period of 5 days. Details of the data collected can be found in Appendix C.

4.1 DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

With the help from colleagues, friends, and the university alumnus, 214 survey responses were received. Basic demographics were collected such as their gender, age group, highest education level, citizenship, current employment level, years of service, industries, and the staff strength.

The demographic breakdown of the respondents is shown in the table 9 in terms of frequency and percentage. With 111 (52%) male respondents and 103 (48.0%) female respondents, there was no statistically significant gender difference among the 214 respondents. However, as shown in Figure 6, there were some differences when we break them into their age group. In the Generation X age group (36% of the overall respondents), there were 77 respondents, and in them, there were 48 (63%) male respondents and 29 (37%) female respondents. In the Generation Y (Millennial) age group (30% of the overall respondents), there were 65 respondents, and in them, there were 28 (43%) male respondents and 37 (57%) female respondents. In the Generation Z age group (34% of the overall respondents), there were 72 respondents, and in them, there were 35 (49%) male respondents and 37 (51%) female respondents.

Figure 6 : Demographic Profile (Age Group & Gender)

From the total respondents, 73 respondents (34%), work at the Executive/Professional level, which is their present job title. Following this are 35 respondents (16%) who work in senior management, 54 respondents (25%) who are in middle management, and 18 respondents (8%) who are non-executive. Those that Just started / Entry level made up of 15 respondents (7%), and others position is also made up of 15 respondents (7%). Most respondents have ten years and above working experience, making up a total of 81 (38%) respondents. 28 respondents (13%) with 7 to 9 years of work experience are followed by 40 respondents (19%) with four to six years of work experience. The next highest number of respondents are 65 respondents (30%) with one to three years.

Demographic Profile of 214 respondents		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	<i>Male</i>	111	52%
	<i>Female</i>	103	48%
Age Group	<i>18 to 25 years old</i>	72	34%
	<i>26 to 41 years old</i>	65	30%
	<i>42 to 57 years old</i>	77	36%
Educational level	<i>Secondary</i>	3	1%
	<i>Diploma</i>	44	21%
	<i>Bachelor's Degree</i>	123	57%
	<i>Master's Degree</i>	43	20%
	<i>PhD and above</i>	1	0%
Citizenship	<i>Singaporean</i>	194	91%
	<i>Singapore PR</i>	14	7%
	<i>Others</i>	6	3%
Cuurent position	<i>Owner / C-suite</i>	4	2%
	<i>Senior Management</i>	35	16%
	<i>Middle Management</i>	54	25%
	<i>Executive/Professional</i>	73	34%
	<i>Non-Executive</i>	18	8%
	<i>Just started / Entry level</i>	15	7%
	<i>Others</i>	15	7%
Years of Service	<i>1 to 3 years</i>	65	30%
	<i>4 to 6 years</i>	40	19%
	<i>7 to 9 years</i>	28	13%
	<i>10 yrs and above</i>	81	38%

Table 12 : Demographic details of the respondents

4.2 MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION

Values on the 5-point Likert scale were used. These are arranged as Strongly agree (5), Agree (4), Neutral (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly disagree (1). These values are tabulated using MS Excel to have the Mean and Standard Deviation calculated. These values will be used in the later section for the hypotheses testing. As there are three distinct age group respondents, the calculation was further breakdown into their individual groups.

On section B: Transformational Leadership style, as shown in table 10 below, the highest mean obtained was from question 2 (Gen X: $M = 4.60$ & $SD = 0.520$, Millennial: $M = 4.72$ & $SD = 0.484$, Gen Z: $M = 4.86$ & $SD = 0.348$). The question is on the communication from the leaders. Another high mean was from question 5 (Gen X: $M = 4.57$ & $SD = 0.548$, Millennial: $M = 4.69$ & $SD = 0.465$, Gen Z: $M = 4.86$ & $SD = 0.348$) which talked about mentorship. These could indicate that respondents prefer more communication and having mentorship in their workplace. However, the lowest mean came from question 4 which talks about the company values (Gen X: $M = 4.43$ & $SD = 0.637$, Millennial: $M = 4.54$ & $SD = 0.588$, Gen Z: $M = 4.68$ & $SD = 0.470$).

Nevertheless, according to the survey, the respondents have indicated the support of a transformational leadership style as the standard deviation of all the five questions were low (with high Mean) and were 'Agree' or 'Strongly agree' to the characteristic of the leadership style. According to Andrade (2020), when the standard deviation is low, the data are clustered around the mean, and when it is large, the data are widely spread. A near-zero standard deviation indicates that data points are close to the mean, whereas a high or low standard deviation signifies that data points are, respectively, above or below the mean (Andrade, 2020).

No.	Questions	Overall Respondents			Generation X Respondents			Millennial Respondents			Generation Z Respondents		
		N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	<i>Is open to innovation.</i>	214	4.55	0.577	77	4.45	0.597	65	4.52	0.589	72	4.69	0.464
2	<i>Always listen and easy to communicate.</i>	214	4.72	0.481	77	4.60	0.520	65	4.72	0.484	72	4.86	0.348
3	<i>believes that each team member may determine their own path to success.</i>	214	4.60	0.594	77	4.45	0.575	65	4.62	0.521	72	4.83	0.411
4	<i>use values as guiding frameworks to aid individuals in making decisions and selecting amongst options.</i>	214	4.52	0.626	77	4.43	0.637	65	4.54	0.588	72	4.68	0.470
5	<i>mentor and nurture us to learn and grow.</i>	214	4.70	0.489	77	4.57	0.548	65	4.69	0.465	72	4.86	0.348

Table 13 : Mean and Standard Deviation for the Transformational Leadership Style Survey

On section C: Team Leadership style, as shown in table 11 below, the highest mean obtained was from question 1 (Gen X: $M = 1.79$ & $SD = 0.412$, Millennial: $M = 2.29$ & $SD = 0.701$, Gen Z: $M = 3.60$ & $SD = 0.705$). The survey question is on 'private' communication from the leaders and had received mixed results from the respondents. From the survey, the matured worker does not prefer 'private' communication from the leaders ('Disagree' and 'Strongly disagree' to the question). However, some of the younger generation gave a different view and have mixed answer to this question. Although the Mean value for the Generation Z is 3.60, it has a standard deviation of 0.705. According to Andrade (2020), higher deviation could mean data points are above the Mean. For this case, they prefer 'private' communication from the leaders. Still, this will require further analysis in the later section.

In contrast, the lowest mean was from question 4 (Gen X: $M = 1.57$ & $SD = 0.498$, Millennial: $M = 1.95$ & $SD = 0.738$, Gen Z: $M = 3.19$ & $SD = 1.109$). But it has the same trend as question 1 where senior respondents does not agree that leaders are 'not accountable for the team's accomplishment and mistakes. And most of the Generation Z respondents choose "Neutral' on this question. Since they do not want to make the cognitive effort to form an opinion, respondents may select a neutral or uncertain response (Demars & Erwin, 2005).

No.	Questions	Overall Respondents			Generation X Respondents			Millennial Respondents			Generation Z Respondents		
		N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	prefer 'private' communication.	214	3.19	1.068	77	1.79	0.412	65	2.29	0.701	72	3.60	0.705
2	encourage individual contribution and less co-operation between employees.	214	2.89	1.180	77	1.68	0.470	65	2.20	0.642	72	3.51	0.856
3	Need longer duration to decide on work activities.	214	2.73	1.117	77	1.73	0.445	65	1.94	0.704	72	3.36	0.893
4	is not accountable for the team's accomplishments and mistakes.	214	2.56	1.235	77	1.57	0.498	65	1.95	0.738	72	3.19	1.109
5	depend on individual to motivate themselves and create passion of their work.	214	2.94	1.181	77	1.75	0.438	65	2.05	0.738	72	3.53	0.964

Table 14 : Mean and Standard Deviation for the Team Leadership Style Survey

On section D: Actualised Leadership style, as shown in table 12 below, the highest mean obtained was different for the three age groups. For the Generation X age group, they had answered question 4 with the highest Mean ($M = 2.45$ & $SD = 0.527$). They had voted 'Disagree' to be serious to work with. Both the Millennial and the Generation Z age group had answered question 5 with the highest Mean. However, their responds were contrasting from each other. For question 5 (promote team activities), the Millennial employees ($M = 1.98$ & $SD = 0.696$) 'Disagree' to Strongly 'Disagree' to promoting team activities. This answer does conflict with the earlier section on the Team Leadership style where Millennial employees prefer teamwork. According to Myers and Sadaghiani (2010), from the earlier studies, Millennial feel more at ease working in groups. Millennial value cooperation and most of them prefer a collaborative work atmosphere over a competitive one (Myers and Sadaghiani, 2010). Surprisingly, for the Generation Z age group, they had answered question 5 with the highest Mean ($M = 4.29$ & $SD = 0.615$), they preferred their manager to promote team activities.

No.	Questions	Overall Respondents			Generation X Respondents			Millennial Respondents			Generation Z Respondents		
		N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	show concerned over their own concerns and less concerned with other issues.	214	2.76	1.265	77	2.03	0.716	65	1.46	0.588	72	3.60	0.781
2	like to work on complicated issues.	214	3.21	1.121	77	2.37	0.610	65	1.85	0.667	72	3.75	0.599
3	check on individual status (education, political beliefs, race, or color) before befriending anyone.	214	2.50	1.324	77	1.95	0.715	65	1.32	0.471	72	3.89	0.491
4	is serious to work with.	214	3.45	1.028	77	2.45	0.527	65	1.92	0.620	72	3.78	0.537
5	promote team activities.	214	3.87	1.043	77	2.43	0.550	65	1.98	0.696	72	4.29	0.615

Table 15 : Mean and Standard Deviation for the Actualised Leadership Style Survey

On section E: Agile Leadership style, as shown in table 13 below, the respondents had answered consistently for all the 5 questions with at least 'Agreed' or 'Strongly Agreed'. Overall, the highest mean obtained was from question 1 and 5 ($M = 4.61$ & $SD = 0.647$ and $M = 4.61$ & $SD = 0.617$ respectively). From Generation X respondents, the highest mean is on question 4 ($M = 4.41$ & $SD = 0.742$) which they 'Agreed' or 'Strongly Agreed' that they do not want 'micro' management from their leaders. Similarly for the Millennial respondents, the highest mean is also on question 4 ($M = 4.75$ & $SD = 0.501$). The younger age group, Generation Z respondents, have the most consistent results on all the 5 questions, with highest mean on question 2 ($M = 4.85$ & $SD = 0.362$).

With the surveyed results, these could indicate that respondents prefer Agile leadership style from their leaders. All the 5 questions were answered with mean of near '5' which they 'Strongly Agree' to the Agile leadership characteristic. In the later section, we should analysis further statistically to verify these results.

No.	Questions	Overall Respondents			Generation X Respondents			Millennial Respondents			Generation Z Respondents		
		N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	promote continuous learning.	214	4.61	0.647	77	4.37	0.612	65	4.71	0.522	72	4.83	0.375
2	encourage feedback and useful criticism.	214	4.56	0.674	77	4.31	0.638	65	4.63	0.575	72	4.85	0.362
3	encourage cross-functional collaboration.	214	4.53	0.669	77	4.37	0.585	65	4.58	0.635	72	4.71	0.542
4	do not micromanage.	214	4.60	0.761	77	4.41	0.742	65	4.75	0.501	72	4.81	0.464
5	accept changes and adapt the change quickly.	214	4.61	0.617	77	4.40	0.680	65	4.66	0.509	72	4.82	0.387

Table 16 : Mean and Standard Deviation for the Agile Leadership Style Survey

On section F, motivational factors were surveyed. The highest mean from the overall respondents come from question 3 ($M = 4.51$ & $SD = 0.774$). However, when the mean is calculated from the 3 different age groups, the responds are different. The senior respondents, with the highest mean from question 4 ($M = 4.25$ & $SD = 0.790$), feel that they are more motivated with enjoyment from their tasks and responsibilities. This is similar to the younger generation, Generation Z respondents, who also have the highest mean from question 4 ($M = 4.83$ & $SD = 0.444$). However, according to the statistic, the Generation Z respondents feel 'Strongly Agree' on their tasks and responsibilities as the standard deviation are lowest. But for the Millennial, they appreciate more from their leaders with recognition and appreciation. Their highest mean is on question 3 ($M = 4.83$ & $SD = 0.444$).

Working from home was becoming more popular before the coronavirus epidemic as more businesses realized the advantages it may have for their companies and the better work-life balance it can provide for their employees. However, as employees move towards the post pandemic, all the respondents are 'Neutral' towards working from home. The motivation factors on 'working from home' appears to be the lowest mean ($M = 3.71$ & $SD = 0.844$). This could also indicate that employees are acceptable to Hybrid working environment than a must to 'Work from Home'. Employees are not required to work exclusively from home when the trend toward remote work shifts. The most effective option is frequently to divide their time between home or other remote places and their place of employment.

No.	Questions	Overall Respondents			Generation X Respondents			Millennial Respondents			Generation Z Respondents		
		N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	<i>I am satisfied and motivated with the current salary.</i>	214	3.90	0.880	77	3.73	0.963	65	3.94	0.788	72	4.19	0.573
2	<i>I am motivated if there is incentive or variable bonus program.</i>	214	4.45	0.802	77	4.08	0.850	65	4.60	0.703	72	4.74	0.628
3	<i>I am motivated with recognition/appreciation from my boss.</i>	214	4.51	0.774	77	4.20	0.930	65	4.65	0.571	72	4.81	0.464
4	<i>I am motivated with enjoyment from my tasks and responsibilities.</i>	214	4.49	0.768	77	4.25	0.790	65	4.55	0.662	72	4.83	0.444
5	<i>'Work from Home' is a must.</i>	214	3.71	0.844	77	3.48	0.811	65	3.82	0.827	72	3.96	0.740

Table 17 : Mean and Standard Deviation for the Motivation factors Survey

4.3 RELIABILITY TEST

According to Taber (2018), the reliability, or internal consistency, of a group of scale or test items is evaluated using the Cronbach's alpha statistic. In other words, the degree to which a measurement is consistent in expressing a notion is what is meant by the term "reliability," and Cronbach's alpha is a metric used to assess the degree of consistency. The internal reliability of the survey questions used in this study was evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha. According to Taber (2018), as show in table 18, the score of over 0.8 is consider good and a good consistency. However, there are certain restrictions to Cronbach's alpha, scores with fewer items tend to be less reliable, and sample size might have a positive or negative impact on the findings.

Cronbach's alpha Criteria	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$	Good
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable

Table 18 : Cronbach's Alpha Criteria

For section B, the Transformational Leadership styles, five questions were used, and the Cronbach's Alpha shown 0.883. In section C, the Team Leadership styles, five questions were used, and the Cronbach's Alpha shown 0.939. In section D, the Actualised Leadership styles, five questions were also used, and the Cronbach's Alpha shown 0.839. In section E, the Agile Leadership styles, five questions were used, and the Cronbach's Alpha shown 0.912. In section F, on the motivation factors, five questions were used, and the Cronbach's Alpha shown 0.844.

Survey	Cronbach's Alpha Score	Internal Consistency
Transformational Leadership Style	0.883	Good
Team Leadership Style	0.939	Excellent
Actualized Leadership Style	0.839	Good
Agile Leadership Style	0.912	Excellent
Motivational factors	0.844	Good

Table 19: Internal Consistency Scoring using Cronbach's Alpha

4.4 HYPOTHESIS TESTING

With the research results, to evaluate the study hypothesis, we will examine the correlation between the independent variables X1, X2, X3, and X4 and the dependent variable Y. Figure 7 shows the research model and to ascertain the correlation and percentage of effect between the X and Y variables, Pearson correlation and regression analysis will be used.

Figure 7 : Research Model of Leadership Styles for Millennial & Generation Z Employee

The primary hypothesis is tested against the null and alternative sub-hypotheses, which are designated by the letters "H_{no}" and "H_{n1}" accordingly, where n is the hypothesis under consideration. With regard to the hypothesis, if the alternate hypothesis H_{11} is determined to be false, the null hypothesis H_{10} must be true. Below is the null and alternate hypothesis for the main hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1 (H₁): The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Transformational Leadership.

H_{10} : Leadership traits that adhere to the Transformational Leadership style do not positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.

H_{11} : Leadership traits that adhere to the Transformational Leadership style do positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Team Leadership.

H₂₀: Leadership traits that adhere to the Team Leadership style do not positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.

H₂₁: Leadership traits that adhere to the Team Leadership style do positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Actualized Leadership.

H₃₀: Leadership traits that adhere to the Actualized Leadership style do positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.

H₃₁: Leadership traits that adhere to the Actualized Leadership style do not positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Agile Leadership.

H₄₀: Leadership traits that adhere to the Agile Leadership style do not positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.

H₄₁: Leadership traits that adhere to the Agile Leadership style do positively affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.

4.4.1 HYPOTHESIS 1

In this section, H1: 'The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Transformational Leadership' will be analysed.

The analysis is applied to assess the leadership styles (independent variable) that could motivate the employee (Y, dependent variable) who are in the Millennial and Generation Z generations. The analysis will be break into 3 portions: - both generations together, Millennial and Generation Z individually.

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.590199904
R Square	0.348335926
Adjusted R Square	0.343508785
Standard Error	0.381155264
Observations	137

Table 20: Regression Analysis of Millennial and Generation Z for H1

Figure 8: Scatter Graph of Millennial and Generation Z for H1

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	10.48364008	10.48364008	72.16194963	3.20503E-14
Residual	135	19.61271028	0.145279335		
Total	136	30.09635036			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	1.026168224	0.400037759	2.565178417	0.011404666
Transformational	0.719626168	0.084713538	8.494818988	3.20503E-14

Table 21: P-value of Millennial and Generation Z for H1

	Transformational
Mean	4.706569343
Variance	0.148853585
Observations	137
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	136
t Stat	142.7858251
P(T<=t) one-tail	2.4093E-150
t Critical one-tail	1.656134988
P(T<=t) two-tail	4.8186E-150
t Critical two-tail	1.977560777

Table 22: T-test results of Millennial and Generation Z for H1

According to the regression test (with both the age group together), the Transformational Leadership style accounts for 35% of the variation in employee motivation with an R^2 value of 0.348. This leadership style and the employee motivation are correlated at $r=0.590$, which accounts for the low positive (moderate) correlation between the X1 and Y variables. Figure 8 above illustrates this relationship's strength visually by showing data points that are near the line of best fit. The coefficient's accuracy as a predictor is strong, with $t = 8.49 (> +2)$. Also, the test results indicated that H_{10} must be rejected because the P-value is 0.0000. The low P-value identification, an alpha value of 0.05 and below indicated that the H_{10} hypothesis is to be rejected. The one-tail t-findings tests led to the conclusion that H_{11} is true whereas H_{10} is false. By rejecting the null hypothesis, we may say that there is a statistically significant relationship between the two variables.

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.542855911
R Square	0.29469254
Adjusted R Square	0.283497184
Standard Error	0.439867387
Observations	65

Table 23: Regression Analysis of Millennial for H1

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.620615791
R Square	0.38516396
Adjusted R Square	0.375404658
Standard Error	0.317698292
Observations	65

Table 24: Regression Analysis of Generation Z for H1

Figure 9: Scatter Graph of Millennial for H1

Figure 10: Scatter Graph of Generation Z for H1

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	5.093012492	5.093012	26.32275	2.98549E-06
Residual	63	12.18944905	0.193483		
Total	64	17.28246154			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	1.394981699	0.570929342	2.443353	0.017365
Transformational	0.631333076	0.123053207	5.13057	2.99E-06

Table 25: P-value of Millennial for H1

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	4.457994668	4.457995	44.20244	5.42823E-09
Residual	70	7.05978311	0.100854		
Total	71	11.51777778			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	0.543762275	0.597067748	0.910721	0.365568
Transformational	0.827768764	0.12450475	6.648491	5.43E-09

Table 26: P-value of Generation Z for H1

	Transformational
Mean	4.618461538
Variance	0.199653846
Observations	65
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	64
t Stat	83.33264547
P(T<=t) one-tail	2.72992E-67
t Critical one-tail	1.669013025
P(T<=t) two-tail	5.45983E-67
t Critical two-tail	1.997729654

Table 27: T-test results of Millennial for H1

	Transformational
Mean	4.786111111
Variance	0.091635368
Observations	72
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	71
t Stat	134.1582737
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.87377E-87
t Critical one-tail	1.666599658
P(T<=t) two-tail	3.74754E-87
t Critical two-tail	1.993943368

Table 28: T-test results of Generation Z for H1

According to the regression analysis for the Millennial and Generation Z age group, the Transformational Leadership style accounts for 30% and 39% of the variation in employee motivation with an R^2 value of 0.295 and 0.385 respectively. This leadership style and the employee motivation are correlated at $r=0.542$ and $r=0.621$ for the Millennial and Generation Z respectively, which accounts for the positive (moderate) correlation between the X1 and Y variables. Figure 9 and 10 above illustrates these relationship's strength visually by showing data points that are near the line of best fit. The coefficient's accuracy as a predictor is strong, with $t = 5.13 (> +2)$ and $t=6.65 (> +2)$ for the Millennial and Generation Z respectively. Also, the test results indicated that H_{10} must be rejected because both P-value is 0.0000. The low P-value identification, an alpha value of 0.05 and below indicated that the H_{10} hypothesis is to be rejected. The one-tail t-findings tests led to the conclusion that H_{11} is true whereas H_{10} is false. By rejecting the null hypothesis, we may say that there is a statistically significant relationship between the two variables.

Hypothesis 1	Both Age Group	Millennials	Generation Z
Leadership traits that adhere to the Transformational Leadership style do affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE
Correlation Relationship of Transformational Leadership style and the employee motivation	Low Positive (35%)	Low Positive (30%)	Low Positive (39%)

Table 29: Verifying Hypothesis 1

The findings demonstrated that Hypothesis 1 is True in all instances involving "Overall", "Millennial", and "Generation Z" samplings. Among these cases, the Generation Z sampling has recorded the highest correlation value ($r=0.621$). Transformational Leadership style satisfied and could positively affect the motivation of the Generation Z employee more than the Millennial employees.

4.4.2 HYPOTHESIS 2

The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Team Leadership.

The analysis is applied to assess the leadership styles (X2, independent variable) that could motivate the employee (Y, dependent variable) who are in the Millennial and Generation Z generations. The analysis will be break into 3 portions: - both generations together, Millennial and Generation Z individually.

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.109639308
R Square	0.012020778
Adjusted R Square	0.004702413
Standard Error	0.469314463
Observations	137

Table 30: Regression Analysis of Millennial and Generation Z for H2

Figure 11: Scatter Graph of Millennial and Generation Z for H2

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	0.36178154	0.36178154	1.642549726	0.20217284
Residual	135	29.73456883	0.220256065		
Total	136	30.09635036			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	4.265308993	0.12211634	34.92824137	1.78002E-69
Team	0.05285143	0.041237989	1.281619961	0.20217284

Table 31: P-value of Millennial and Generation Z for H2

	Team
Mean	2.797080292
Variance	0.952344354
Observations	137
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	136
t Stat	33.54812181
P(T<=t) one-tail	6.00617E-68
t Critical one-tail	1.656134988
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.20123E-67
t Critical two-tail	1.977560777

Table 32: T-test results of Millennial and Generation Z for H2

According to the regression test (with both the age group together), the Team Leadership style accounts for 1% of the variation in employee motivation with an R² value of 0.012. For Low R-squared values, despite the independent variable's importance, it does not account for much of the dependent variable's mean (Frost, et al., 2018). This is because low R-squared values show that the independent variable does not describe much of the variance of the dependent variable (Frost, et al., 2018). This leadership style and the employee motivation are correlated at r=0.110, which accounts for the very low positive (moderate) correlation between the X2 and Y variables. Figure 11 above illustrates this relationship's strength visually by showing data points, when the variance accounts are low, the data points tend to fall farther from the line of best fit (Frost, et al., 2018). The coefficient's accuracy as a predictor is weak, with t = 1.282 (> +2). Also, the test results indicated that H₂₀ is accepted because the P-value is 0.202. The high P-value identification, an alpha value of 0.05 and above indicated that the H₂₀ hypothesis is to be accepted. The one-tail t-findings tests led to the conclusion that H₂₁ is false whereas H₂₀ is true. By accepting the null hypothesis, we may say that the hypothesis test is not statistically significant.

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.262716529
R Square	0.069019974
Adjusted R Square	0.054242514
Standard Error	0.505362144
Observations	65

Table 33: Regression Analysis of Millennial for H2

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.138199799
R Square	0.019099184
Adjusted R Square	0.005086316
Standard Error	0.40174259
Observations	72

Table 34: Regression Analysis of Generation Z for H2

Figure 12: Scatter Graph of Millennial for H2

Figure 13: Scatter Graph of Generation Z for H2

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1.192835053	1.192835	4.670625	0.034491012
Residual	63	16.08962649	0.255391		
Total	64	17.28246154			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	4.783828523	0.227689264	21.01034	3.71E-30
Team	-0.22676146	0.104925671	-2.16116	0.034491

Table 35: P-value of Millennial for H2

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	0.219980162	0.21998	1.362975	0.246984013
Residual	70	11.29779762	0.161397		
Total	71	11.51777778			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	4.261876744	0.214027183	19.91278	1.51E-30
Team	0.070859751	0.060695395	1.167465	0.246984

Table 36: P-value of Generation Z for H2

According to the regression analysis individually for the Millennial and Generation Z age group, the Actualized Leadership style accounts for 7% and 2% of the variation in employee motivation with an R^2 value of 0.069 and 0.019 respectively. Low R-squared values show that the independent variable does not describe much of the variance of the dependent variable (Frost, et al., 2018). This leadership style and the employee motivation are correlated at $r=0.263$ and $r=0.138$ for the Millennial and Generation Z respectively, which accounts for the low positive (moderate) correlation between the X2 and Y variables. Figure 12 and 13 above illustrates these relationship's strength visually by showing data points that are spread further from the line of best fit. The coefficient's accuracy as a predictor is weak, with $t = -2.16 (> +2)$ and $t=1.16 (> +2)$ for the Millennial and Generation Z respectively.

	Team
Mean	2.086153846
Variance	0.362461538
Observations	65
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	64
t Stat	27.93650331
P(T<=t) one-tail	7.2464E-38
t Critical one-tail	1.669013025
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.44928E-37
t Critical two-tail	1.997729654

Table 37: T-test results of Millennial for H2

	Team
Mean	3.438888889
Variance	0.617057903
Observations	72
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	71
t Stat	37.14680215
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.46569E-48
t Critical one-tail	1.666599658
P(T<=t) two-tail	2.93138E-48
t Critical two-tail	1.993943368

Table 38: T-test results of Generation Z for H2

The test results indicated that the P-value is 0.03 for the Millennial and P-value is 0.24 for the Generation Z. H_{20} is false for the Millennial because its P-value is less than 0.05. However, P-value is above 0.05 for the Generation Z which indicate H_{20} is true. The higher P-value identification, an alpha value of 0.05 and below indicated that the H_{20} hypothesis is to be rejected for the Millennial but otherwise for the Generation Z. The one-tail t-findings tests led to the conclusion that there is a statistically significant relationship between the two variables for the Millennial but not statistically significant for the Generation Z. It will be suggested to discontinue using this collection of independent variables if the "Significance F" value exceeds 0.05 (Frost, et al., 2018).

Hypothesis 2	Both Age Group	Millennials	Generation Z
Leadership traits that adhere to the Team Leadership style do not affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.	TRUE	FALSE	TRUE
Correlation Relationship of Team Leadership style and the employee motivation	Low Positive (1%)	Low Positive (7%)	Low Positive (2%)

Table 39: Hypothesis Verifying H2

The findings demonstrated that Hypothesis 2 is True involving "Overall" and "Generation Z" samplings. It is False for the Millennial age group as Team Leadership style does have some effect on their motivation. Among these cases, the Millennial sampling has recorded the highest correlation value ($r=0.263$). However, Team Leadership style do not positively affect the motivation of the Generation Z employees.

4.4.3 HYPOTHESIS 3

The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Actualized Leadership.

The analysis is applied to assess the leadership styles (X3, independent variable) that could motivate the employee (Y, dependent variable) who are in the Millennial and Generation Z generations. The analysis will be break into 3 portions: - both generations together, Millennial and Generation Z individually.

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.201344284
R Square	0.040539521
Adjusted R Square	0.033432406
Standard Error	0.462491311
Observations	137

Table 40: Regression Analysis of Millennial and Generation Z for H3

Figure 14: Scatter Graph of Millennial and Generation Z for H3

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	1.220091614	1.220091614	5.70407577	0.018309636
Residual	135	28.87625875	0.213898213		
Total	136	30.09635036			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	4.179204202	0.105619022	39.56866959	3.83854E-76
Actualized	0.082388237	0.034496304	2.388320701	0.018309636

Table 41: P-value of Millennial and Generation Z for H3

	Actualized
Mean	2.839416058
Variance	1.321670245
Observations	137
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	136
t Stat	28.90864669
P(T<=t) one-tail	3.11694E-60
t Critical one-tail	1.656134988
P(T<=t) two-tail	6.23388E-60
t Critical two-tail	1.977560777

Table 42: T-test results of Millennial and Generation Z for H3

According to the regression test (with both the age group together), the Actualize Leadership style accounts for 4% of the variation in employee motivation with an R² value of 0.041. For Low R-squared values, despite the independent variable's importance, it does not account for much of the dependent variable's mean (Frost, et al., 2018). This is because low R-squared values show that the independent variable does not describe much of the variance of the dependent variable (Frost, et al., 2018). This leadership style and the employee motivation are correlated at r=0.201, which accounts for the very low positive (moderate) correlation between the X1 and Y variables. Figure 14 above illustrates this relationship's strength visually by showing data points, when the variance accounts are low, the data points tend to fall farther from the line of best fit (Frost, et al., 2018). The coefficient's accuracy as a predictor is slightly weak, with t = 2.39 (> +2). Also, the test results indicated that H₃₀ must be rejected because the P-value is 0.0183. The low P-value identification, an alpha value of 0.05 and below indicated that the H₃₀ hypothesis is to be rejected. The one-tail t-findings tests led to the conclusion that H₃₁ is true whereas H₃₀ is false. By rejecting the null hypothesis, we may say that there is a statistically significant relationship between the two variables.

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.11649321
R Square	0.013570668
Adjusted R Square	-0.00208694
Standard Error	0.52019421
Observations	65

Table 43: Regression Analysis of Millennial for H3

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.19323168
R Square	0.037338482
Adjusted R Square	0.023586175
Standard Error	0.397989975
Observations	72

Table 44: Regression Analysis of Generation Z for H3

Figure 15: Scatter Graph of Millennial for H3

Figure 16: Scatter Graph of Generation Z for H3

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	0.234534547	0.234535	0.866714	0.355420525
Residual	63	17.04792699	0.270602		
Total	64	17.28246154			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	4.558705752	0.274023842	16.63616	9.79E-25
Actualized	-0.145188053	0.155952731	-0.93097	0.355421

Table 45: P-value of Millennial for H3

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	0.430056341	0.430056	2.71507	0.103886538
Residual	70	11.08772144	0.158396		
Total	71	11.51777778			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	3.713166485	0.483174362	7.684941	6.94E-11
Actualized	0.205223069	0.124547677	1.647747	0.103887

Table 46: P-value of Generation Z for H3

According to the regression analysis individually for the Millennial and Generation Z age group, the Actualized Leadership style accounts for 1% and 4% of the variation in employee motivation with an R^2 value of 0.014 and 0.037 respectively. Low R-squared values show that the independent variable does not describe much of the variance of the dependent variable (Frost, et al., 2018). This leadership style and the employee motivation are correlated at $r=0.116$ and $r=0.193$ for the Millennial and Generation Z respectively, which accounts for the low positive (moderate) correlation

between the X3 and Y variables. Figure 15 and 16 above illustrates these relationship's strength visually by showing data points that are spread near the line of best fit. The coefficient's accuracy as a predictor is weak, with $t = -0.93 (> +2)$ and $t=1.65 (> +2)$ for the Millennial and Generation Z respectively.

	Actualized
Mean	1.707692308
Variance	0.173846154
Observations	65
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	64
t Stat	33.02050851
P(T<=t) one-tail	3.24366E-42
t Critical one-tail	1.669013025
P(T<=t) two-tail	6.48732E-42
t Critical two-tail	1.997729654

Table 47: T-test results of Millennial for H3

	Actualized
Mean	3.861111111
Variance	0.143818466
Observations	72
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	71
t Stat	86.39154107
P(T<=t) one-tail	5.75431E-74
t Critical one-tail	1.666599658
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.15086E-73
t Critical two-tail	1.993943368

Table 48: T-test results of Generation Z for H2

The test results indicated that the P-value is 0.36 for the Millennial and P-value is 0.10 for the Generation Z. H_{30} is true for both Millennial and Generation Z because its P-value are more than 0.05. The higher P-value identification, an alpha value of 0.05 and above indicated that the H_{30} hypothesis is to be accepted for both the Millennial and Generation Z. These high P-value led to the conclusion that it is not statistically significant between the two variables for both the Millennial and Generation Z. However, it will be suggested to discontinue using this collection of independent variables if the "Significance F" value exceeds 0.05 (Frost, et al., 2018).

Hypothesis 3	Both Age Group	Millennials	Generation Z
Leadership traits that adhere to the Actualized Leadership style do not affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
Correlation Relationship of Actualized Leadership style and the employee motivation	Low Positive (4%)	Low Positive (1%)	Low Positive (4%)

Table 49: Hypothesis Verifying H3

The findings demonstrated that Hypothesis 3 is True involving "Overall" and "Generation Z" samplings. It is False for both the Millennial and Generation Z age group as Actualized Leadership style does have some effect on their motivation. Among these cases, the 'Overall' sampling has recorded the highest correlation value ($r=0.201$).

4.4.4 HYPOTHESIS 4

In this section, H4: 'The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Agile Leadership' will be analysed.

The analysis is applied to assess the leadership styles (X4, independent variable) that could motivate the employee (Y, dependent variable) who are in the Millennial and Generation Z generations. The analysis will be break into 3 portions: - both generations together, Millennial and Generation Z individually.

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.561837866
R Square	0.315661788
Adjusted R Square	0.310592616
Standard Error	0.390593874
Observations	137

Table 50: Regression Analysis of Millennial and Generation Z for H4

Figure 17: Scatter Graph of Millennial and Generation Z for H4

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	9.500267772	9.500267772	62.27087813	9.13088E-13
Residual	135	20.59608259	0.152563575		
Total	136	30.09635036			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	1.319141577	0.393500005	3.352329249	0.001039895
Agile	0.652922988	0.082740752	7.891189906	9.13088E-13

Table 51: P-value of Millennial and Generation Z for H4

	Agile
Mean	4.738686131
Variance	0.163860026
Observations	137
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	136
t Stat	137.0192917
P(T<=t) one-tail	6.3105E-148
t Critical one-tail	1.656134988
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.2621E-147
t Critical two-tail	1.977560777

Table 52: T-test results of Millennial and Generation Z for H4

For the last regression test (with both the age group together), the Agile Leadership style accounts for 32% of the variation in employee motivation with an R^2 value of 0.316. This leadership style and the employee motivation are correlated at $r=0.562$, which accounts for the low positive (moderate) correlation between the X1 and Y variables. Figure 17 above illustrates this relationship's strength visually by showing data points that are near the line of best fit. The coefficient's accuracy as a predictor is strong, with $t = 7.89 (> +2)$. Also, the test results indicated that H_{40} must be rejected because the P-value is 0.0000. The low P-value identification, an alpha value of 0.05 and below indicated that the H_{40} hypothesis is to be rejected. The one-tail t-findings tests led to the conclusion that H_{41} is true whereas H_{40} is false. By rejecting the null hypothesis, we may say that there is a statistically significant relationship between the two variables.

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.612818973
R Square	0.375547094
Adjusted R Square	0.365635143
Standard Error	0.413887557
Observations	65

Table 53: Regression Analysis of Millennial for H4

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.438941251
R Square	0.192669422
Adjusted R Square	0.181136128
Standard Error	0.364469364
Observations	72

Table 54: Regression Analysis of Generation Z for H4

Figure 18: Scatter Graph of Millennial for H4

Figure 19: Scatter Graph of Generation Z for H3

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	6.490378205	6.490378	37.88831	5.76713E-08
Residual	63	10.79208333	0.171303		
Total	64	17.28246154			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	1.126041667	0.519932538	2.165746	0.034123
Agile	0.682291667	0.110845339	6.155348	5.77E-08

Table 55: P-value of Millennial for H3

ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	2.219123586	2.219124	16.7055	0.000114764
Residual	70	9.298654192	0.132838		
Total	71	11.51777778			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	1.930478589	0.631491437	3.057015	0.003164
Agile	0.536164088	0.131180114	4.087236	0.000115

Table 56: P-value of Generation Z for H3

According to the regression analysis each individual age group (for the Millennial and Generation Z), the Agile Leadership style accounts for 38% and 19% of the variation in employee motivation with an R^2 value of 0.376 and 0.193 respectively. This leadership style and the employee motivation are correlated at $r=0.613$ and $r=0.439$ for the Millennial and Generation Z respectively, which accounts for the positive (moderate) correlation between the X1 and Y variables. Figure 18 and 19 above illustrates these relationship's strength visually by showing data points that are near the line of best fit. The coefficient's accuracy as a predictor is strong, with $t = 6.16$ ($> +2$) and $t=4.09$ ($> +2$) for the Millennial and Generation Z respectively.

	Agile
Mean	4.667692308
Variance	0.217846154
Observations	65
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	64
t Stat	80.62764032
P(T<=t) one-tail	2.21219E-66
t Critical one-tail	1.669013025
P(T<=t) two-tail	4.42438E-66
t Critical two-tail	1.997729654

Table 57: T-test results of Millennial for H4

	Agile
Mean	4.802777778
Variance	0.10872457
Observations	72
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0
df	71
t Stat	123.5932897
P(T<=t) one-tail	6.18401E-85
t Critical one-tail	1.666599658
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.2368E-84
t Critical two-tail	1.993943368

Table 58: T-test results of Generation Z for H4

Also, the test results indicated that H₄₀ must be rejected because both P-value is 0.0000. The low P-value identification, an alpha value of 0.05 and below indicated that the H₄₀ hypothesis is to be rejected. The one-tail t-findings tests led to the conclusion that H₄₁ is true whereas H₄₀ is false. By rejecting the null hypothesis, we may say that there is a statistically significant relationship between the two variables.

Hypothesis 4	Both Age Group	Millennials	Generation Z
Leadership traits that adhere to the Agile Leadership style do affect employee motivation for the Millennial and Generation Z generations.	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE
Correlation Relationship of Agile Leadership style and the employee motivation	Low Positive (32%)	Low Positive (38%)	Low Positive (19%)

Table 59: Hypothesis Verifying H4

The findings demonstrated that Hypothesis 4 is True in all instances involving "Overall", "Millennial", and "Generation Z" samplings. Among these cases, the Millennial sampling has recorded the highest correlation value (r=0.613). Agile Leadership style satisfied and could positively affect the motivation of the Generation Z employee more than the Millennial employees.

4.4.5 HYPOTHESIS ANALYSIS SUMMARY

From the analysis, the four hypotheses turned out to be true as shown in table 45 below. However, it is crucial to keep in mind that, as with all quantitative study, the statistical findings are not always accurate and that the conclusions are only valid for the range attained (Borgstede and Scholz, 2021).

Hypothesis	Results
H1: The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Transformational Leadership.	TRUE
H2: The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Team Leadership	TRUE
H3: The Millennial and Generation Z generations are not motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Actualized Leadership.	TRUE
H4: The Millennial and Generation Z generations are motivated at work when their leaders exhibit traits that support Agile Leadership.	TRUE

Table 60: Summary of Hypothesis Testing

Also shown in Table 46 below, the testing resulted with positive correlation between the X and Y variables.

Hypothesis / Correlation	Both Age Group	Millennials	Generation Z
<i>Correlation Relationship of Transformational Leadership style and the employee motivation</i>	Low Positive (35%)	Low Positive (30%)	Low Positive (39%)
<i>Correlation Relationship of Team Leadership style and the employee motivation</i>	Low Positive (1%)	Low Positive (7%)	Low Positive (2%)
<i>Correlation Relationship of Actualized Leadership style and the employee motivation</i>	Low Positive (4%)	Low Positive (1%)	Low Positive (4%)
<i>Correlation Relationship of Agile Leadership style and the employee motivation</i>	Low Positive (32%)	Low Positive (38%)	Low Positive (19%)

Table 61: Overall Hypothesis Testing

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 RESEARCH QUESTION AND OBJECTIVE ONE

RQ1. Is Transformational or Team leadership style preferred by the Millennial and Generation Z employees?

RO1. To identify the leadership style to manage Millennial and Generation Z employee.

Beginning with James V. D. in 1973, James Burns elaborated on the idea of transformative leadership in 1978. Researcher Bernard M. Bass further developed the idea in 1985 by adding criteria for determining transformational leadership effectiveness (Whites, et al., 2022). With the hope that their followers would be motivated to do the same, this leadership development approach pushes leaders to show strong and real leadership. The five traits of this leadership style were surveyed to determine if the Millennial and Generation Z employee prefer these traits in their working environment.

Question 2 and 5 have the highest mean which respondents had chosen 'Agree' or 'Strongly Agree' to these traits. Both Generation does agree they would prefer their leaders to 'always listen and easy to communicate' (Question 2). According to Dagostina (2021), leaders must talk to Generation Z in a direct, relatable, and intimate manner if Leaders want to engage them. Despite the development of the virtual tools, Generation Z employees appear to still choose in-person interactions in the office. (Jha, et al., 2023). On Question 5, Generation Z also responded towards 'Strongly Agree' and agree to have the mentorship which help them to grow. According to Segal (2022), Generation Z appreciate having a boss who is equally concerned with their personal and professional growth.

Figure 20: Mean Results of the Surveyed Questions on Transformational Leadership Style for Millennial and Generation Z

Although the lowest mean was on question 1 ($M = 4.52$), the analysis has shown that this leadership style is agreeable to both Millennial and Generation Z. In term of Mean and standard deviation calculation, the results are on either 'Agreed' or 'Strongly Agree'. Also, under the Regression and P-value, the respondents results are statistically significant. In conclusion, the research question (RQ1) and research objectives (RO1) are answered that Transformational Leadership style is preferred by both Millennial and Generation Z employees.

Figure 21: Mean Results of the Surveyed Questions on Team Leadership Style for Millennial and Generation Z

Based on the research, statistically, Millennial employees prefer the Team Leadership style as well from their leaders. There is much research that tally to this finding. According to Arnold (2016), throughout elementary school, the Millennial generation has worked in teams. And most Millennial prefer working in groups if given the option. A welcoming and cooperative work environment is also appealing to Millennial. They may express any thoughts or opinions they may have in the working environment without worrying about being judged by their co-workers or more seasoned team members (Buddy and Sendek, 2014). Even with the Regression and P-value statistical calculation, it also shown that Millennial employees has some effect with Team Leadership style.

In contrast, Generation Z is not fully in preference for Team Leadership style. In fact, the Generation Z respondents had answered 'Neutral' or 'Agreed' to the 5 questions on this Leadership style. The Mean value is from 3.19 to 3.60. According to McCrindle and Fell (2019), Generation Z employees are individuals and cannot be considered as a group or team. The recent pandemic could have made an impact on the mindset of the Generation Z employees. Working alone might not be efficient and without the cooperation in a team, work could be delayed. Still, further study with focused on Generation Z on teamwork would help answer this puzzle.

5.2 RESEARCH QUESTION AND OBJECTIVE TWO

RQ2. Is Agile or Actualized leadership style preferred by the Millennial and Generation Z employees?

RO2. To identify the modern leadership style to manage Millennial and Generation Z employee.

The survey results for the Actualized Leadership style have the similar trend as the Team Leadership style. The Millennial employees prefer the Actualized Leadership style as well from their leaders. According to Sparks (2019), this leadership profiling is based on Abraham Maslow's concept of 'self-actualization'. This leadership style was not popular as other leadership style as it required further training so that Leaders could apply this style effectively. Statistically, Generation Z also appreciate and motivated with this leadership style. However, the high P-value led to the conclusion that it is not statistically significant between the two variables for both the Millennial and Generation Z. As such, it will be suggested to discontinue using this collection of independent variables if the "Significance F" value exceeds 0.05 (Frost, et al., 2018).

Figure 22: Mean Results of the Surveyed Questions on Actualized Leadership Style for Millennial and Generation Z

The visionary and coach are the two of the new leadership positions that McKinsey believes this contemporary leadership style should embrace. The agile mentality enters the picture here. Today's leaders must be open to change and able to make sense of their environment (Bozickovic, et al., 2022). According to Focardi (2022), several members of Generation Z feel that the conventional hierarchical structure, in which they see that promotions were usually granted purely on the basis of length of service, is not a realistic option and that an agile manner of working is the only practical alternative.

According to Bozickovic (2022), many organizations are moving away from the conventional, plan-driven culture where ideas, answers, and choices are made by one person—a leader—or have already done so. In those organizations, a more inclusive agile strategy involves a larger range of business stakeholders and greater brainpower.

From the survey results, it is not surprised that both Millennial and Generation Z are receptive of Agile Leadership style, which is the current modern leadership styles. Flexibility and adaptivity is one of the appealing benefits of agile leadership (Bozickovic, et al., 2022). Generation Z employees prefer that their leaders ‘do not micromanage’, this is the highest mean ($M = 4.75$) obtained. Furthermore, the Millennial employees shows a greater supporter to the Agile Leadership with their survey results towards ‘Strongly Agree’ to its traits.

Figure 23: Mean Results of the Surveyed Questions on Agile Leadership Style for Millennial and Generation Z

It is conclusive that, statistically, both Millennial and the Generation Z employees prefer the Agile leadership style. Although the preference is visible, they might not understand the disadvantage of the Agile Leadership. According to Bozickovic (2022), It's simple to misunderstand how agile leadership works. For instance, many continue to believe that Scrum is the sole kind of agile. It may be argued that Scrum is the most widely used framework to result from an agile strategy. Agile, though, is much more than that; it's about altering one's perspective and being more receptive to alternative approaches (Bozickovic, et al., 2022).

5.3 RESEARCH QUESTION AND OBJECTIVE THREE

RQ3. What are the motivation factors for Millennial and Generation Z employees?

RO3. To discover the motivation factor for Millennial and Generation Z employees

According to Guzman (2022), the two most significant characteristics for new Singaporean employees were work-life balance and employee well-being, but high pay failed to rank in the top five in Singapore while being ranked third globally by respondents. According to the interview between Mr. Chiew Chun Wee (head of policy at the Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA) for ASEAN and ANZ) and Singapore business Review, he mentioned that Generation Z is starting their careers at a time when the economy is struggling. The pandemic's seismic pressures have changed the way they think and behave. Given the difficulties the world faces, such as job instability and isolation, it is not surprising that their survey revealed that employment security and opportunity, personal wellness, and mental health were the top two concerns among this age group globally, particularly in the Asia Pacific region and Singapore (Guzman, et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, in our survey, 'incentive or variable bonus program' (Question 2) is one of the motivators for both the Millennial and Generation Z employees who had answered towards 'Agree' and 'Strongly Agree' to this question. Furthermore, on Question 3 and 4, the respondents also 'Agree' and 'Strongly Agree' that 'recognition/appreciation from' their leader and the 'enjoyment on their tasks and responsibilities' does align with the findings from the article by Guzman (2022). Though these are the highest mean among the 5 questions, and we could conclude that these are the motivation factors influencing the two age group employees, it is noted that further study is required as there are other factors not surveyed here. Each generation tends to acquire a collective personality that impacts how people live their lives, including how they feel, even if each individual within a generation is distinct. Involvement in and goals for work, attitudes toward authority and organizations, and even how one plans to fulfil one's goals.

Figure 24: Mean Results of the Surveyed Questions on Motivation Factors for Millennial and Generation Z

This study has focused on the impact of leadership styles on employee's motivation. The focus was on only four types of leadership styles- transformational, team, actualised and agile. According to the study, team and actualized leadership styles were shown to have a detrimental impact on younger employees, whilst transformational and agile leadership styles were found to have a favourable impact. The results of this study show that the leadership style of an organization affects employee motivation in both good and bad ways. Employee opportunity, a sense of belonging, and participation in decision-making are all vital components of a leadership style. In this situation, it is advised that firms concentrate on implementing transformational and agile leadership philosophies to enhance organizational performance.

5.4 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE STUDY

Each theoretical perspective offers different methods of seeing and not perceiving, and each theoretical perspective has advantages and disadvantages. One can better understand leadership and the elements that influence leadership results in practice by comprehending and applying a variety of theoretical lenses. According to Hackman and Johnson (2013), the techniques occasionally conflict with one another and occasionally they overlap. Each method provides valuable information, but none of them provides a general explanation of how leaders behave. Employee motivation is not a leader's responsibility (Hackman and Johnson, 2013). A leader's job is to find out what is demoralizing the workforce and eliminate it. Future leaders will spend a significant amount of time here, if not many of it. Once-helpful management structures and workplace practices are readily transformed into barriers. The leader continuously assesses these and removes any obstacles as rapidly as feasible (Hackman and Johnson, 2013).

By 2025, Generation Z will make up a quarter of the global labour force, according to the World Economic Forum. Every leader's responsibility is to inspire, direct, and restrain followers' enthusiasm and effectiveness (Kotter, 1998). The traits and methods used by different leaders to apply their leadership styles vary. According to Naile and Selesho (2014), leaders are thought to be effective when the traits of their followers are reflected in their leadership style. As a result, for their employees to reach their full potential, they must be conscious of the impact that their actions have on their followers' opinions of and attitudes about the workplace. Generation Z has grown weary of businesses that solely care about their money. Rather, they keep asking for more and more in return. People anticipate that you will talk to them directly rather than to some fictitious audience in your communications (Naile and Selesho, 2014).

On the other hand, transformative leadership supports agile workplaces, especially in circumstances when the risk of failure is reduced. Developing and maintaining an existing product should be consistent and error-free, even if you don't want it to obstruct the growth and development of forthcoming updates and upgrades.

It is therefore, recommended to further research on the youngest employees' expectation on motivation in their workplaces. More complete list of both monetary and non-monetary compensation should be investigated. Also, the effectiveness on the type of leadership style for each generation should be further analyse and research in each different industry. Also, the research should be done after certain leadership style is applied which would provide a much practical respond.

5.5 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

Deep understanding of how leadership styles affect employee motivation has been made available by this study. The fact that only quantitative data has been used is one of its drawbacks. The research's reach and usefulness have been greatly constrained as a result. So, to ascertain the link between leadership style and employee motivation, future study should concentrate on applying pertinent research methodologies in addition to qualitative approaches.

Even though the analysis of the study verified the research assumptions, this research acknowledged its limitations. Initially, the sample size (N= 214) was viewed as being tiny, made even more so by further lowering when not all specify industries and age groups were survey. An improved balance of responses was suggested by a larger number of significant samples. The random sample was further constrained by number of questions asked for each leadership styles and the motivation factors. As a result, common styles and factors was asked. Because participation in the poll is entirely optional, it's possible that people will answer casually. In fact, there are 216 respondents and 2 of them were removed due to their irregular respond.

The research's main results were constrained by generation Z's lack of sufficient work experience to allow them to establish a solid view about leadership and associated techniques. As most of them are just starting out in their jobs and haven't had a lot of opportunities, their opinions and views are more likely to shift with time.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abulela, M. A. A., & Harwell, M. M. (2020). Data analysis: Strengthening inferences in quantitative education studies conducted by novice researchers. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 20(1), 59 - 78. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12738/jestp.2020.1.005>
- Andrade C. (2020). Understanding the Difference Between Standard Deviation and Standard Error of the Mean and Knowing When to Use Which. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*. 2020;42(4):409-410. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0253717620933419>
- Amabile, T.M. and Kramer, S.J. (2011). *The Progress Principle, Using Small Wins to Ignite Joy, Engagement, and Creativity at Work*. Boston/Harvard Business Review Press.
- Akkaya, B. (2020) *Agile business leadership methods for industry 4. 0*. Bingley: Emerald Publishing Limited. Available at: <http://public.eblib.com/choice/PublicFullRecord.aspx?p=6357744> (Accessed on 13 Feb 2023).
- Ali, Ameer. (2021). *Quantitative Data Analysis*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23322.36807>.
- Arnold, K., et al. (2016). Are Millennial Good Team Players? Available at: <https://extraordinaryteam.com/are-Millennial-good-team-player/> (Accessed on 27 Mar 2023)
- Aslam, A., Eugster J., Ho G., Jaumotte F., & Piazza R., et al. (2018). Globalization Helps Spread Knowledge and Technology Across Borders Available at: <https://www.imf.org/en/Blogs/Articles/2018/04/09/globalization-helps-spread-knowledge-and-technology-across-borders> (Accessed on 20 Feb 2023)
- Awang, N., et al. (2022). The Big Read: Generational gap — a bridge too far or are we making too much of it? Available at: <https://www.channelnewsasia.com/singapore/big-read-generational-gap-bridge-too-far-or-are-we-making-too-much-it-2713451> (Accessed on 9 Feb 2023)
- Benítez, MD, Sánchez, T.E.M, Bermúdez, G. and Núñez-Rydman E.S. (2022) Generation Z Within the Workforce and in the Workplace: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Front. Psychol.* 12:736820. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.736820
- Berger, R. (2015). Now I see it, now I don't: Researcher's position and reflexivity in qualitative research. *Qualitative Research*, 15 (2), 219-234. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794112468475>
- Borgstede, M. and Scholz, M. (2021) Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches to Generalization and Replication—A Representationalist View. *Front. Psychol.* 12:605191. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.605191
- Bouchrika, I., et al. (2022). How to Write a Research Question: Types, Steps, and Examples. *Research.com Academy*. 14 Oct 2022. Available at: <https://research.com/research/how-to-write-a-research-question/> (Accessed on 11 Feb 2023)

Buddy, H. J. W. and Sendek, H. (2014). *Gen Y Now: Millennial and the Evolution of Leadership*, 2nd Edition. CA: Wiley

Bozickovic, A., et al. (2022). Modern Leadership Styles — What Does It Mean to Be a Truly “Agile” Leader? Available at: <https://www.servicedeskintstitute.com/modern-leadership-styles-what-does-it-mean-to-be-a-truly-agile-leader/> (Accessed on 27 Mar 2023)

Chala, N., Poplavska, O., Danylevych, N., Levseitseva, O. and Sova R. (2022). Intrinsic motivation of Millennial and generation Z in the new post-pandemic reality. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 20(2), 536-550. doi:10.21511/ppm.20(2).2022.44

Chhotray, S., Sivertsson, O. and Tell, J. (2018). The Roles of Leadership, Vision, and Empowerment in Born Global Companies. *J Int Entrep* 16, 38–57 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10843-017-0201-8>

Creswell, J. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*, (4th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education.

Christensen, L.B., Johnson, R.B., & Turner, L.A. (2019). *Research methods, design, and analysis* (13th ed.). Boston, NJ: Pearson.

Claypool, K.K., et al. (2017). Organizational success: how the presence of happiness in the workplace affects employee engagement that leads to organizational success (2017). *Theses and Dissertations*. 783. Available at: <https://digitalcommons.pepperdine.edu/etd/783> (Accessed on 22 Feb 2023)

Clemons, D., et al. (2014). Look to Millennial to lead. *Public Relations Tactics*, 21(8), 9. Available at: http://www.prsa.org/Intelligence/Tactics/Issues/view/22/12#.VnsN5_krLaQ (Accessed on 22 Feb 2023)

Creswell, J.W. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches*, 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Dagostina, A., et al. (2021). Here Is How Gen Z Is Changing The Way We Communicate. *Fobes Communications Council*. 9 Aug 2021. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbescommunicationscouncil/2021/08/09/here-is-how-gen-z-is-changing-the-way-we-communicate/?sh=640be9581350> (Accessed on 27 Mar 2023)

DeMars, C. E., & Erwin, T. D. (2005). Neutral or unsure: Is there a difference?. Poster presented at the annual meeting of the American Psychological Association, Washington, DC.

Ferri, R.J. et al. (2014). Are Millennial employees changing how managers manage? *Journal for Quality & Participation*, 37(2), 15-35. Available at: <http://asq.org/pub/jqp/> (Accessed on 25 Feb 2023)

- Focardi, R., et al. (2022). Still adapting to Gen Z workers? We need to start thinking about working with Gen Z leaders. Available at: <https://www.channelnewsasia.com/commentary/how-work-gen-z-employees-leaders-boss-3035191/> (Accessed on 27 Mar 2023)
- Fournier, A.B. et al. (2020). What Is the Difference Between Quantitative and Qualitative Research? verywellmind, 30 Apr 2022. Available at: <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-the-difference-between-quantitative-andqualitative-research-4588136> (Accessed on 26 Feb 2023)
- Frost, J. et al. (2018). How to Interpret Regression Models that have Significant Variables but a Low R-squared, Statistics By Jim. Available at: <https://statisticsbyjim.com/regression/low-r-squared-regression/> (Accessed on 21 Mar 2023)
- Gizachew, T. (2014) Social Revolutions: Their Causes, Patterns, and Phase. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2158244014548845>
- Gigliotti, R.A. (Ed.). (2019). Leadership competencies: A framework for leadership assessment, education, and research. Bingley: Emerald Group Publishing.
- Grover, V. (2014). Research Approach: An Overview. Golden Research Thoughts. Vol 4, Issue 5. Available at: <https://aygrt.isrj.org> (Accessed on 25 Mar 2023)
- Goleman, D. (1998). Working with emotional intelligence. New York, NY: Bantam Books.
- Guzman, L.D., et al. (2022). Gen Z: The trials and tribulations of seeking employment. HR & Education, Singapore. Available at: <https://sbr.com.sg/hr-education/exclusive/gen-z-trials-and-tribulations-seeking-employment> (Accessed on 25 Feb 2023)
- Harlez, R. (2015). Management by Objectives: Get the best out of your employees Management & Marketing. 50minutes/Lemaitre Publishing
- Hackman, M.Z. and Johnson, C.E. (2013). Leadership: A communication perspective (6th Ed.). Long Grove, IL: Waveland Press
- Hesselbein, F., Goldsmith, M. and Leader to Leader Institute (2006). The leader of the future 2 : visions, strategies, and practices for the new era. 1st edn. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass (J-B Leader to Leader Institute/PF Drucker Foundation, v. 84).
- Human Resource Management International Digest (HRMID) (2019). The Next Generation: The differing role of employee development in creating organizational commitment in Generation Xers and Millennial", Human Resource Management International Digest, Vol. 27 No. 7, pp. 42-44. <https://doi.org/10.1108/HRMID-06-2019-0174>
- Indeed Editorial Team (2022) Basic Research vs. Applied Research (Including Examples) Available at: <https://sg.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/basic-research-vs-applied-research> (Accessed: 18 Aug 2022).

Jha, M., et al. (2023). Communicating with Generation Z in the Workplace. 23 Mar 2023. Available at: <https://www.contactmonkey.com/blog/gen-z-employees> (Accessed on 27 Mar 2023).

John, B., et al. (2019). Making An Impact Through Effective Technology Leadership, 9 Sep 2019. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2019/09/09/making-an-impact-through-effective-technology-leadership/?sh=3b5b8c385259> (Accessed on 21 Feb 2023)

Journal Of Indian Management, 12(3), 94-103. Available at: <http://www.scmsgroup.org/scmsjim/about-us.html> (Accessed on 25 Feb 2023)

Julian, B.A., Annelies, G.B., Bruch, C., and Wolf, C. (2022) Split Questionnaire Designs for Online Surveys: The Impact of Module Construction on Imputation Quality, *Journal of Survey Statistics and Methodology*, Volume 10, Issue 5, November 2022, Pages 1236–1262, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jssam/smab055>

Kelley, K., Clark, B., Brown, V. and Sitzia, J. (2003), Good practice in the conduct and reporting of survey research, *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, Volume 15, Issue 3, May 2003, Pages 261–266, <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzg031>

Kendra, C., et al. (2022). Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. Maslow believed that physiological and psychological needs motivate our actions, *verywellmind*, 14 Aug 2022. Available at: <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-maslows-hierarchy-of-needs-4136760> (Accessed on 17 Aug 2022)

Kenrick, D.T, Griskevicius, V., Neuberg, S.L. and Schaller, M. (2010). Renovating the pyramid of needs: Contemporary extensions built upon ancient foundations. *Perspect Psychol Sci.* 2010;5(3):292-314. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691610369469>

Khajeh, E.H.A. (2018)," Impact of Leadership Styles on Organizational Performance", *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*, Vol. 2018 (2018), Article ID 687849, <https://doi.org/10.5171/2018.687849>

Larkin, S., et al. (2017). What Motivates Millennial and Generation Z? An investigation into the motivation and associated rewards which impact the two generational age cohorts: Millennial and Gen Z, *National College of Ireland*, Aug 2017. (Accessed on 17 Aug 2022)

Leavy, P. (2014). *The Oxford Handbook of Qualitative Research*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press. doi: 10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199811755.001.0001

Lee, M.R. (2021). *Leading Virtual Project Teams. Adapting Leadership theories and communications Techniques to 21st Century Organizations*. 2nd Edition. New York/CRC Press.

Lee, S., et al. (2020). What is transactional leadership? *Leadership Development*, 8 Apr 2020. Available at: <https://torch.io/blog/what-is-transactional-leadership/> (Accessed on 21 Aug 2022)

Lipkin, N.A. and Perrymore, A.J. (2009). *Y in the Workplace: Managing the "Me First" Generation*. NJ: Career Press

Maslow, A.H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*. 1943;50(4):370-396. doi:10.1037/h0054346

Maslow, A.H. (2019). *A Theory of Human Motivation. A Psychological Research that Helped Change the Field for Good*. 1st Edition. New Delhi: General Press.

McCrindle, M. and Fell, A. (2019). *Understanding Generation Z: Recruiting, Training and Leading the Next Generation*. Australia: McCrindle Research Pty Ltd. ISBN-13: 978-0-6486695-0-0

McGiboney, G. W. (2018) *Leadership theories and case studies: an epidemiological perspective*. Newcastle upon Tyne, UK: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

Myers, K.K. and Sadaghiani, K (2010). Millennial in the Workplace: A Communication Perspective on Millennial' Organizational Relationships and Performance. *J Bus Psychol*. 2010 Jun;25(2):225-238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-010-9172-7>.

Navene, E., et al. (2022). 2 in 5 employees won't accept jobs that don't offer remote working or flexible hours: Survey, Todayonline, 15 Aug 2022. Available at: <https://www.todayonline.com/singapore/work-home-flexible-hours-workforce-survey-1969876> (Accessed on 16 Aug 2022)

Neufeld, D., et al. (2021). A Regional Breakdown of Millennial Around the World, Visual Capitalist, 1 Nov 2021. Available at: <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/sp/a-regional-breakdown-of-Millennial-around-the-world/> (Accessed on 17 Aug 2022)

Pandis, N. (2016). The chi-sqaure test. *Statistics and Research Design*, Volume 150, Issue 5, P898-899 Nov 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajodo.2016.08.009>

Pieter, D. and Steven, F., et al. (2020) *Beyond Maslow's Pyramid: Introducing a Typology of Thirteen Fundamental Needs for Human-Centered Design*. doi:10.3390/mti4030038

Patel, M. and Patel, N. (2019) *Exploring research methodology: review article*. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2019; 6(3):48-55.

Parker, D. W., Holesgrove, M., and Pathak, R. et al. (2015). Improving productivity with self-organised teams and agile leadership. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 64(1), 112–128.

Petro, G., et al. (2021). Gen Z Is Emerging As The Sustainability Generation: Survey, Forbes, 30 Apr 2021. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/gregpetro/2021/04/30/gen-z-is-emerging-as-the-sustainability-generation/?sh=e2057dd86995> (Accessed on 8 Feb 2023)

Rana, R. and Singhal, R. (2015) Chi-square test and its application in hypothesis testing. *J Pract Cardiovasc Science*; 1:69-71. Available from: <https://www.j-pcs.org/text.asp?2015/1/1/69/157577> (Accessed on 06 Mar 2023)

- Roopa, S. and Rani, M.S. (2012). Questionnaire Designing for a Survey. *The Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society*, October-December 2012;46(4):273-277
- Ruben, B.D. (2006). *What leaders need to know and do: A leadership competencies scorecard*. Washington, DC: National Association of College and University Business Officers.
- Ruben, B. D. and Gigliotti, R. A. (2019) *Leadership, communication, and social influence: a theory of resonance, activation, and cultivation*. Bingley: Emerald Publishing Limited (Emerald Points Ser). Available: <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/roehampton-ebooks/reader.action?docID=5889410> (Accessed on 14 Feb 2023).
- Rumsey, M. G. (ed.) (2013) *The oxford handbook of leadership*. New York: Oxford University Press (Oxford library of psychology).
- Sauser, W.I. and Sims, R. (2013). *Managing Human Resources for the Millennial Generation*. North Carolina/IAP.
- Scheunpflug, A., Krogull, S., and Franz, J. (2016). Understanding learning in world society: qualitative reconstructive research in global learning and learning for sustainability. *Int. Journal Dev. Educ. Glob. Learn.* 7, 6–23. doi: 10.18546/IJDEGL.07.3.02
- Schermerhorn, J.R. (2011). *Introduction to Management*. 11th Edition. USA/Wiley.
- Schroth, H. (2019). Are You Ready for Gen Z in the Workplace? *California Management Review* 2019, Vol. 61(3) 5-18. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0008125619841006>
- Schrage, M., et al. (2016). Like It or Not, You Are Always Leading by Example. *Harvard Business Review*. 5 Oct 2016. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2016/10/like-it-or-not-you-are-always-leading-by-example> (Accessed on 20 Feb 2023)
- Segal, E., et al. (2022). How And Why Managing Gen Z Employees Can Be Challenging For Companies. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/edwardsegal/2022/03/25/how-and-why-managing-gen-z-employees-can-be-challenging-for-companies/?sh=909d3fc44d26> (Accessed on 9 Feb 2023)
- Shashi, S., Ajay, S. and Kiran, S., et al. (2012). Motivation Levels among Traditional and Open Learning Undergraduate Students in India. June 2012 Available at: <https://www.irrodl.org/index.php/irrodl/article/view/1050/2196> (Accessed on 22 Feb 2023)
- Sirisilla, S., et al. (2022). How to Develop a Good Research Question? — Types & Examples. *Enago Academy*. 19 Dec 2022. Available at: <https://www.enago.com/academy/how-to-develop-good-research-question-types-examples/> (Accessed on 11 Feb 2023)
- Singapore Institute of Technology (no date) Food, Chemical and biotechnology. Available at: <https://www.singaporetech.edu.sg/food-chemical-and-biotechnology/applied-research> (Accessed: 18 Aug 2022).

Singapore University of Social Sciences (no date) SUSS - USE Survey on Security Officers. <https://www.suss.edu.sg/about-suss/centres/centre-for-applied-research/suss-union-of-security-employees> (Accessed: 18 Aug 2022).

Sparks, W. L. (2019) *Actualized leadership: meeting your shadow and maximizing your potential*. First edn. Alexandria, VA: Human Resource Management

Sreejesh, S., Mohapatra, S., Anusree, M.R. (2014). Questionnaire Design. In: *Business Research Methods*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-00539-3_5

Taber, K. (2018). The Use of Cronbach's Alpha When Developing and Reporting Research Instruments in Science Education. *Research in Science Education* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-016-9602-2>

Taherdoost, H. (2022). What are Different Research Approaches? Comprehensive Review of Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Method Research, Their Applications, Types, and Limitations. *Journal of Management Science & Engineering Research*, 5(1): 53-63, 2022 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30564/jmser.v5i1.4538>

Taherdoost1, H. (2022). Designing a Questionnaire for a Research Paper: A Comprehensive Guide to Design and Develop an Effective Questionnaire. *Asian Journal of Managerial Science*, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.51983/ajms-2022.11.1.3087>

Taylor, C. M., Cornelius, C. J. and Colvin, K., et al. (2013). Visionary leadership and its relationship to organizational effectiveness. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 35(6), 566–583.

Thomas, M.T. (1998). *Management by Objectives*, The Pfeiffer Library Volume 20, 2nd Edition. Jossey-Bass/Pfeiffer.

Tomaszewski, L. E., Zarestky, J., & Gonzalez, E. (2020). Planning Qualitative Research: Design and Decision Making for New Researchers. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406920967174>

Trivedy, D. (2018) *Our classrooms : perceptiveness and its implications for transformational leadership*. New York: Business Expert Press.

Vives, P. J., et al. (2018) *Leading with Agility: 9 fundamental principles you must know*. Harvard Business Review. 23 Jul 2018. Available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/leading-agility-9-fundamental-principles-you-must-pere-juarez-vives/> (Accessed on 21 Feb 2023)

Yadav, D. (2022) *Criteria for Good Qualitative Research: A Comprehensive Review*. *Asia-Pacific Edu Res* 31, 679–689 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-021-00619-0>

Whites S. K., et al. (2022) *What is transformational leadership? A model for motivating innovation*. Foundry. 10 Oct 2022. Available at: <https://www.cio.com/article/228465/what-is-transformational-leadership-a-model-for-motivating-innovation.html>. (Accessed on 26 Mar 2023)

Fournier A.B. et al. (2020). What Is the Difference Between Quantitative and Qualitative Research? verywellmind, 30 Apr 2022. Available at: <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-the-difference-between-quantitative-and-qualitative-research-4588136> (Accessed on 18 Aug 2022)

Titulescu N et al. (2013) A quantitative research of consumer's attitude towards food products advertising, 1(2), pp. 1-3.

Galland C et al. (2008) Effective Teacher Leadership: A Quantitative Study Of The Relationship Between School Structures And Effective Teacher Leaders, 1(1), pp. 1-15.

Berg S. & Marques R. et al. (2010) Quantitative Studies of Water and Sanitation Utilities: A Literature Survey, 1(1), pp. 1-32.

Spamann H. et al. (2009) Large-Sample, Quantitative Research Designs for Comparative Law?, The American Journal of Comparative Law Vol. 57, No. 4 (FALL 2009), pp. 797-810 (14 pages).

Charlesworth Author Services (2022) The importance of having Large Sample Sizes for your research. Available at: <https://www.cwauthors.com/article/importance-of-having-large-sample-sizes-for-research> (Accessed: 19 Aug 2022).

Ford J. et al. (2021). What are the characteristics of good research instrument? AnswersToAll, 1 Mar 2021. Available at: <https://answer-to-all.com/language/what-are-the-characteristics-of-good-research-instrument/> (Accessed on 19 Aug 2022)

Poh J. et al. (2018). 4 Jobs Suffering from a High Turnover Rate in Singapore. MoneySmart, 2 Sep 2018. Available at: <https://blog.moneysmart.sg/career/jobs-high-turnover-rate-singapore/> (Accessed on 20 Aug 2022)

APPENDICES

A - LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 : Leader’s Approached and Theories (Ruben and Gigliotti, 2019).....	13
Table 2 : Actualized Performance Framework (Sparks, 2019)	16
Table 3 : Leadership Shadows in the Context of ALP Framework (Sparks, 2019)	17
Table 4 : 9 Attributes of Actualized Leaders	18
Table 5 : Acronym of Articles.....	24
Table 6 : Quantitative, Mixed, and Qualitative Methods (Christensen, Johnson, & Turner, 2019).	29
Table 7 : Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods (Patel and Patel, 2019; Grover, 2015).	31
Table 8 : Survey Questions Formulation	36
Table 9 : Survey Questions Formulation (cont’).....	37
Table 10 : Corresponding Research Objectives, Questions, and the Hypotheses	38
Table 11: Cronbach’s Alpha Score for Piloting Test on Survey Questions	40
Table 12 : Demographic details of the respondents.....	44
Table 13 : Mean and Standard Deviation for the Transformational Leadership Style Survey .	45
Table 14 : Mean and Standard Deviation for the Team Leadership Style Survey.....	46
Table 15 : Mean and Standard Deviation for the Actualised Leadership Style Survey.....	47
Table 16 : Mean and Standard Deviation for the Agile Leadership Style Survey	48
Table 17 : Mean and Standard Deviation for the Motivation factors Survey	49
Table 18 : Cronbach’s Alpha Criteria.....	50
Table 19: Internal Consistency Scoring using Cronbach’s Alpha.....	50
Table 20: Regression Analysis of Millennial and Generation Z for H1.....	53
Table 21: P-value of Millennial and Generation Z for H1.....	53
Table 22: T-test results of Millennial and Generation Z for H1.....	54
Table 23: Regression Analysis of Millennial for H1 Table 24: Regression Analysis of Generation Z for H1	54
Table 25: P-value of Millennial for H1	55
Table 26: P-value of Generation Z for H1	55
Table 27: T-test results of Millennial for H1 Table 28: T-test results of Generation Z for H1	55
Table 29: Verifying Hypothesis 1	56
Table 30: Regression Analysis of Millennial and Generation Z for H2.....	57

Table 31: P-value of Millennial and Generation Z for H2..... 57

Table 32: T-test results of Millennial and Generation Z for H2..... 58

Table 33: Regression Analysis of Millennial for H2 Table 34: Regression Analysis of
Generation Z for H2 58

Table 35: P-value of Millennial for H2..... 59

Table 36: P-value of Generation Z for H2 59

Table 37: T-test results of Millennial for H2 Table 38: T-test results of Generation Z
for H2..... 60

Table 39: Hypothesis Verifying H2 61

Table 40: Regression Analysis of Millennial and Generation Z for H3..... 62

Table 41: P-value of Millennial and Generation Z for H3..... 62

Table 42: T-test results of Millennial and Generation Z for H3..... 63

Table 43: Regression Analysis of Millennial for H3 Table 44: Regression Analysis of
Generation Z for H3 63

Table 45: P-value of Millennial for H3..... 64

Table 46: P-value of Generation Z for H3..... 64

Table 47: T-test results of Millennial for H3 Table 48: T-test results of
Generation Z for H2 65

Table 49: Hypothesis Verifying H3 65

Table 50: Regression Analysis of Millennial and Generation Z for H4..... 66

Table 51: P-value of Millennial and Generation Z for H4..... 66

Table 52: T-test results of Millennial and Generation Z for H4..... 67

Table 53: Regression Analysis of Millennial for H4 Table 54: Regression Analysis of
Generation Z for H4 67

Table 55: P-value of Millennial for H3..... 68

Table 56: P-value of Generation Z for H3..... 68

Table 57: T-test results of Millennial for H4 Table 58: T-test results of Generation
Z for H4..... 69

Table 59: Hypothesis Verifying H4 69

Table 60: Summary of Hypothesis Testing..... 70

Table 61: Overall Hypothesis Testing 70

B - LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 : Nine features of Agile Leadership (Vives, et al., 2018)	20
Figure 2 : Six Leadership Styles (Akkaya, 2020).....	23
Figure 3 : Research Model on Leadership Styles for Millennial & Generation Z Employee.....	28
Figure 4 : Framework for Research (Grover, 2015).	30
Figure 5 : Phases of creating a questionnaire (Roopa and Rani, 2012).....	33
Figure 6 : Demographic Profile (Age Group & Gender)	43
Figure 7 : Research Model of Leadership Styles for Millennial & Generation Z Employee.....	51
Figure 8: Scatter Graph of Millennial and Generation Z for H1	53
Figure 9: Scatter Graph of Millennial for H1	Figure 10: Scatter Graph of Generation Z for H1.....
	55
Figure 11: Scatter Graph of Millennial and Generation Z for H2.....	57
Figure 12: Scatter Graph of Millennial for H2	Figure 13: Scatter Graph of Generation Z for H2
	59
Figure 14: Scatter Graph of Millennial and Generation Z for H3.....	62
Figure 15: Scatter Graph of Millennial for H3	Figure 16: Scatter Graph of Generation Z for H3
	64
Figure 17: Scatter Graph of Millennial and Generation Z for H4.....	66
Figure 18: Scatter Graph of Millennial for H4	Figure 19: Scatter Graph of Generation Z for H3
	68
Figure 20: Mean Results of the Surveyed Questions on Transformational Leadership Style for Millennial and Generation Z.....	71
Figure 21: Mean Results of the Surveyed Questions on Team Leadership Style for Millennial and Generation Z	72
Figure 22: Mean Results of the Surveyed Questions on Actualized Leadership Style for Millennial and Generation Z.....	73
Figure 23: Mean Results of the Surveyed Questions on Agile Leadership Style for Millennial and Generation Z	74
Figure 24: Mean Results of the Surveyed Questions on Motivation Factors for Millennial and Generation Z.....	75

C – FINAL SURVEY

Dissertation Research

Leadership Styles influencing the morale of the Millennials/Generation Z employees: A study on the worker of the future in Singapore.

Hi Everyone,

I am Kok Leong, and I am working on my final dissertation as part of my MBA program at the University of Roehampton under the supervision of Frankie Yee. My research is to investigate the Leadership styles affecting the morale of the Millennials and Generation Z Employees. I would like to invite you to participate in my research.

The estimated time required to complete this questionnaire is about 10-15 minutes. I assure you that all responses collected are anonymous and will be used solely for academic purposes.

Confidentiality:

- This survey does not collect confidential information about you or your company.
- All data obtained here will be reported in an aggregated format.
- Any information you provide will be kept strictly confidential in publishing the results of the investigation.

Kindly share this link with your friends and colleagues so that I can have a wider range of participants.

Please send me an email tengk@roehampton.ac.uk if you have any further questions.

Thank you for your time in advance. Your input and support are greatly appreciated.

Section 1: Demographic Profile

To determine the general information of participants when analyzing the results.

1. Gender *

- Male
- Female

2. Age Group *

- 18 to 25 years old
- 26 to 41 years old
- 42 to 57 years old
- 58 to 70 years old

3. What is your highest education level attained ? *

- Primary
- Secondary / GCE 'O' Level
- College / GCE 'A' Level / Diploma
- Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree
- PhD and above

4. Citizenship *

- Singaporean
- Singapore PR
- Malaysian
- Others

5. What is your current work level ? *

- Owner / C-suite
- Senior Management (eg. Heads, Regional Manager)
- Middle Management (e.g. Manager, Lead)
- Executive / Professional
- Non-Executive
- Just Started / Entry level
- others

6. Years of Service *

- 1 to 3 years
- 4 to 6 years
- 7 to 9 years
- 10 years and above

7. What Industry are you in ? *

- Banking & Finance
- Pharmaceutical & Healthcare
- IT, Comm & Technology
- Wholesale & Retail
- Energy, Oil & Gas
- Food & Beverage / Hospitality & Tourism
- Real Estate / Construction
- Manufacturing, Shipping
- Education / Legal
- Transportation / Logistics
- Public Sector
- Social Service, Non-Profit Orgainsation

7. What Industry are you in ? *

- Banking & Finance
- Pharmaceutical & Healthcare
- IT, Comm & Technology
- Wholesale & Retail
- Energy, Oil & Gas
- Food & Beverage / Hospitality & Tourism
- Real Estate / Construction
- Manufacturing, Shipping
- Education / Legal
- Transportation / Logistics
- Public Sector
- Social Service, Non-Profit Orgainsation

8. Company Staff Strength *

- 1 to 50
- 51 to 100
- 101 to 500
- 501 to 1000
- more than 1000

Next

Page 1 of 6

Clear form

Transformational Leadership

In this section, the survey is on how would this leadership influence your morale in your daily work.

I am motivated at work if my manager..... *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Is open to innovation.	<input type="radio"/>				
Always listen and easy to communicate.	<input type="radio"/>				
believes that each team member may determine their own path to success.	<input type="radio"/>				
use values as guiding frameworks to aid individuals in making decisions and selecting amongst options.	<input type="radio"/>				
mentor and nurture us to learn and grow.	<input type="radio"/>				

Back

Next

Page 2 of 6

Clear form

Team Leadership

In this section, the survey is on how would this leadership influence your morale in your daily work.

I am motivated at work if my manager..... *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
prefer 'private' communication	<input type="radio"/>				
encourage individual contribution and less co-operation between employees.	<input type="radio"/>				
Need longer duration to decide on work activities.	<input type="radio"/>				
is not accountable for the team's accomplishments and mistakes.	<input type="radio"/>				
depend on individual to motivate themselves and create passion of their work.	<input type="radio"/>				

Back

Next

Page 3 of 6

Clear form

Actualized Leadership

In this section, the survey is on how would this leadership influence your morale in your daily work.

I am motivated at work if my manager..... *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
show concerned over their own concerns and less concerned with others issues.	<input type="radio"/>				
like to work on complicated issues.	<input type="radio"/>				
check on individual status (education, political beliefs, race, or color) before befriending anyone.	<input type="radio"/>				
is serious to work with.	<input type="radio"/>				
promote team activities.	<input type="radio"/>				

Back

Next

Page 4 of 6

Clear form

Agile Leadership

In this section, the survey is on how would this leadership influence your morale in your daily work.

I am motivated at work if my manager..... *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
promote continuous learning.	<input type="radio"/>				
encourage feedback and useful criticism.	<input type="radio"/>				
encourage cross-functional collaboration.	<input type="radio"/>				
do not micromanage.	<input type="radio"/>				
accept changes and adapt the change quickly.	<input type="radio"/>				

Back

Next

Page 5 of 6

Clear form

Motivation Factors.

In this section, the survey is on the motivation factors you would prefer in your daily work.

I am motivated if... *

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I am satisfied and motivated with the current salary.	<input type="radio"/>				
There is incentive or variable bonus program.	<input type="radio"/>				
There is recognition/appreciation from my boss	<input type="radio"/>				
I am enjoying my tasks and responsibilities.	<input type="radio"/>				
'Work from Home' is a must.	<input type="radio"/>				

Back

Submit

Page 6 of 6

Clear form

D – RESEARCH DATA

3. What is your highest education level attained ?

216 responses

4. Citizenship

216 responses

5. What is your current work level ?

216 responses

6. Years of Service

216 responses

7. What Industry are you in ?

216 responses

8. Company Staff Strength

216 responses

I am motivated at work if my manager.....

I am motivated at work if my manager.....

BLANK